

Review Panel of GILDA

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Documents for the Review Panel of GILDA

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This report was written by F. d'Acapito, C. Maurizio, S. Mobilio, G. Artioli, A. Balerna, F. Boscherini, P. Fornasini, C. Lamberti, C. Meneghini, S. Quartieri, F. Rocca and with the technical help of V. Tullio.

I. Technical description of the beamline

GILDA Description

The Italian Collaborating Research Group GILDA at ESRF is a general-purpose beamline using a bending magnet source¹. It is financed by three major Italian public research Institutes (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche CNR, Istituto Nazionale per la Fisica della Materia INFN and Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare INFN). GILDA was proposed, builded and commissioned by a collaboration between the Frascati National Laboratories of INFN with a number of Italian Universities namely Cagliari, Camerino, L' Aquila, Roma "Tor Vergata", Roma TRE, Parma, Trento. It is operational since Sept 1994.

GILDA is mainly dedicated to X-ray structural investigations. At this purpose, techniques like X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy as well as X-ray Diffraction are used on the beamline.

GILDA provides to the experiments at the sample position an X-ray beam in the energy range 4 - 90 keV, with an energy resolution $\Delta E/E \approx 10^{-5} - 10^{-4}$, a spot size of about 2*2 mm and a flux up to $10^{10} - 10^{11}$ ph/s.

The beamline consists of four hutches: the first contains the optical elements and the others the experimental apparatus.

The first experimental hutch is dedicated to X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) and is placed in the 1:3 focal configuration to obtain the maximum flux. The wide energy range of the beamline makes GILDA well-suited for XAS investigations on mid-heavy elements with the possibility to access the K absorption edges from Ca to Au and the L edges from Sb and over. Experiments are carried out in transmission, fluorescence and total electron yield modes. For the study of highly diluted samples a 13-elements high purity Ge detector is currently used (current sensitivity limit: 10^{14} at/cm²). Surface experiments in total reflection mode (ReflEXAFS) are performed in a dedicated experimental chamber.

The second hutch, in 1:1 focal geometry, is dedicated to X-ray scattering and diffraction. A two-circle diffractometer is used to carry out powder diffraction and anomalous scattering. For powder diffraction an Imaging Plate detector is also available. A Translating Image Plate system allows to perform time-resolved powder diffraction experiments from few seconds to minutes..

At the end of the beamline a third experimental hutch is available for users who wish to install their own apparatus. An ultra high vacuum chamber fully equipped for surface preparation and characterization is available for surface-EXAFS investigations.

Optics

The beamline, schematically shown in the figure, is equipped with a monochromator and two

Figure 1

¹d'Acapito F., Colonna S., Pascarelli S., Antonioli G., Balerna A., Bazzini A., Boscherini, Campolungo F., Chini G., Dalba G., Davoli I., Fornasini P., Graziola R., Licheri G., Meneghini, Rocca F., Sangiorgio L., Sciarra V., Tullio V., Mobilio S., ESRF Newsletter **30** (1998), 42.

Layout of the optical hutch. A further pair of flat Pt coated mirrors are installed in the XAS hutch for harmonic rejection at the lowest energies.

mirrors one before and the other after the monochromator. The first mirror intercepts 4 mrad of the horizontal fan of radiation at a glancing angle of 3 mrad, reflecting and collimating the beam in the vertical direction to reduce its vertical divergence. The double-crystal fixed-exit monochromator, equipped with Si(111), Si(311) or Si(511) crystals makes the beam monochromatic. The second crystal is sagittally curved to focus the beam in the horizontal plane; dynamical focusing² is used to keep beam dimensions at the focal point constant throughout all the energy range of the beamline. The second mirror focuses the beam in the vertical direction in three focal points E1, E2 and E3 each one set inside one of the three experimental cabins. Both mirrors have a double coating to achieve efficient harmonic rejection in the range 7-21 keV (Pd coating) and in the range 21-27 keV (Pt coating).

The optics of the beamline includes also two small Pt coated mirrors set in the absorption hutch that are used for harmonic rejection in the 4 – 7 keV range.

Schematic view of the sagittally focussing monochromator operative at GILDA provides a monochromatic x-ray photon beam

The beamline works in 4 different optical configurations:

- 1) In the energy range (7-27 keV) both mirrors with the appropriate coating are used and generally Si(311) crystals are mounted in the monochromator.
- 2) At low energies (4 - 7 keV), Si(111) monochromating crystals are used; for an efficient rejection of the harmonics a pair of Pt coated mirrors working at 10 mrad are inserted on the beam.
- 3) At high energy (27 - 50 keV), the mirrors are removed and Si(511) crystals are used.
- 4) At very high energies (50-90 keV) the third order reflection from Si(311) crystals is used coupled to a suitable filtering of the incoming beam for the rejection of the main reflection³.

The XAS hutch

The x-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) hutch has been designed to carry out XAS experiments in different detection geometries and experimental conditions, ranging from concentrated to diluted samples (dilution limit 10 ppm or 10^{14} at/cm²) and from bulk samples to

² Pascarelli S., Boscherini F., D'acapito F., Hrdy J., Meneghini C., Mobilio S., J. Synchrotron Rad. **3** (1996) 147.

³ F. d'Acapito, S.Colonna, C.Maurizio, S.Mobilio, J.Synchrotron Rad. **9** (2002), 24.

surfaces (thickness limit 0.2 ML) forms. The conventional XAS apparatus consists of two experimental high vacuum chambers.

Layout of the EXAFS Hutch

The first chamber is used for standard experiments, while the second one is available for the installation of bulky/heavy cells from the users^{4,5}. Depending on the nature of the samples a number of different detectors are available at the beamline, namely:

- 1) Ion Chambers: two chambers are used for measurements in transmission mode. They can be filled with N, Ar or Kr gases to ensure a good efficiency in the whole energy range.
- 2) High Purity Ge multidetector (13 elements): this detector is used for the collection of high quality fluorescence spectra with a typical energy resolution of 200 eV and maximum count rate of 100 kcps/element. A digital pulse processing permits a fast and reliable calibration of the device as well as an easy correction for dead time effects⁶.
- 3) To perform measurements with surface sensitivity, the detection of electrons with a channeltron multiplier (with possibility to perform partial yield) or with a He chamber is available. It is also possible to measure the drain current from the sample via a current amplifier.

XAS measurements can be carried out in a wide temperature range using a liquid He cryostat (4-300 K), a liquid nitrogen cryo-oven (77-500K) or a graphite oven (500-1000 K). A goniometer mounted on the top of the liquid nitrogen cryostat permits the accurate positioning of the sample respect to the beam polarization direction, so realizing "polarized EXAFS" experiments, whereas the use of a vibrating sample holder helps in minimizing the effect of coherent scattering when analyzing single crystals⁷.

⁴I. Pettiti, D. Gazzoli, M. Inversi, M. Valigi, S. De Rossi, G. Ferraris, P. Porta and S. Colonna, *J. Synchrotron Rad.* **6** (1999) 1120.

⁵ C. Lamberti, C. Prestipino, S. Bordiga, G. Berlier, G. Spoto, A. Zecchina, A. Laloni, F. La Manna, F. D'Anca, R. Felici, F. D'Acapito, P. Roy, *Nucl. Instrum and Meth. B* **200** (2003) 196.

⁶Ciatto G., d'Acapito F., Boscherini F., Mobilio S., *J. Synchrotron Rad.* **11** (2004) 278.

⁷V. Tullio, F. D'Anca, F. Campolungo, F. D'Acapito, F. Boscherini, S. Mobilio, INFN-LNF Internal Note, LNF-01/020 (NT), 2001.

A further experimental chamber is dedicated to total reflection EXAFS (RefLEXAFS) measurements for the investigation of surfaces or buried interfaces⁸.

A picture of the RefLEXAFS chamber

The sample is oriented with the surface parallel to the polarization vector and the incidence angle can be adjusted within $1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ deg. The size of the incident beam is between 100 and 40 μm and an extremely good collimation is obtained by using 2 slits of the desired width at a relative distance of 2m. The intensities of the "incoming" and "specularly reflected" beam are measured by ion chambers whereas the fluorescence signal is collected by the multielement Hp-Ge detector. Samples can be also prepared in situ by evaporation and an oven permits the sample treatment in controlled gas atmosphere up to 700 K.

The X-ray Diffraction Facility

The diffraction hutch is dedicated to (Anomalous) Wide Angle X-ray Scattering (AWAXS and WAXS) on powders and structurally disordered systems⁹. The experimental apparatus is based on a 2-circle diffractometer Seifert MZ VI, with an angular step of 0.2" of arc and a reproducibility of 2" of arc. The diffracted beam is detected using a scintillation detector; a flat/curved Ge crystal analyser is also available. The intensity of the incoming photon-beam is measured using an ionisation chamber. Absorption measurements in transmission mode may also be performed, in order to obtain a correct beam energy calibration.

⁸ F. d'Acapito, I. Davoli, P. Ghigna, S. Mobilio, J. Synchrotron Rad. **10**, (2003) 260.

⁹C. Meneghini, A. Balerna, F. Boscherini, S. Pascarelli and S. Mobilio, J. Synchrotron Rad. **5**, (1998) 1258.

The apparatus for Time resolved x-ray Diffraction

Just after the diffractometer a Translating Image Plate system (TIP) is mounted to carry out experiments of time resolved x-ray diffraction¹⁰. The Image plate has a resolution of $100 * 100 \mu\text{m}$ and is placed at about 30 cm from the sample: this permits the collection of data up to a scattering angle of about 40 deg. Phase transitions can be studied in samples contained in thin capillaries (0.2-1 mm) and undergoing heat treatments via an air blower (up to 1000 deg) or chemical reactions¹¹. In front of the TIP a slit selects a vertical slice of the diffracted beam; the TIP can translate horizontally so permitting the collection of time resolved data. An IP reader is available in the terminal room of the beamline.

In order to perform measurements on catalysts, a specific set-up has been implemented¹¹ to monitor the structural evolution of the sample in reaction environment. The sample is contained in a quartz capillary, supported by an aluminum frame fitted in a goniometer head. The capillary is open on both sides, allowing the reaction gases to enter at one end and the products to be conveyed to a quadrupole mass at the other end. This geometry warrants the optimal experimental conditions as concerns *i.* the absence of dead sample volumes not reached by the gas flow, *ii.* the uniformity of the sample temperature, *iii.* the overcoming of diffusion effects. On the side of the structural analysis, the correspondence between the sample participating to the chemical reaction and that probed by the X-ray beam is therefore ensured.

Time resolved XRD experiments are also performed in Grazing Incidence mode to enhance the scattering signal from the surface layer of a sample. An oven permits to carry out sample treatments in-situ, in vacuum ($p < 3 * 10^{-5}$ mbar) or in controlled atmosphere up to 1250 °C. The oven is mounted on a dedicated rotation/translation stage for a precise alignment.

Third Hutch

¹⁰C. Meneghini, G. Artioli, A. Balerna, A. F. Gualtieri, P. Norby and S. Mobilio, J. Synchrotron Rad. **8**, (2001) 1162.

¹¹A. Martorana, G. Deganello, A. Longo, F. Deganello, L. Liotta, A. Macaluso, G. Pantaleo, A. Balerna, C. Meneghini and S. Mobilio, J. Synchrotron Rad. **10** (2003). 177.

The third experimental hutch was conceived for users wishing install their own apparata on the beamline. At present, an apparatus dedicated to EXAFS in Ultra High Vacuum conditions is mounted.

Picture of the UHV chamber.

It consists in an UHV chamber, capable to reach a base pressure of 10^{-10} mbar, containing an angular resolved electron detector, an Auger electron analysis system and a manipulator to align the sample and keep it at temperatures between LNT and 700 K. A side chamber is used for sample preparation using an evaporator and a transfer arm connects the two chambers. Detectors like multielement HP-Ge or a channeltron can be used for the collection of surface EXAFS data.

II. Staff and associated roles

Gilda Staff and associated roles and interests

Gilda has two kinds of staff, the staff at Grenoble and the Italian collaborators.

At Grenoble there are present: two scientist, one PHD student, a full technician and a partial time technician. An additional scientist is going to be appointed.

Francesco D' Acapito has a permanent position as beamline scientist. He is responsible of the every day activity of the beamline at Grenoble; his scientific activity regards mainly the study of optoelectronic materials, nanostructured systems and quantum dots.

Chiara Maurizio has a two years position as a scientist to be renewed at the end of 2004; her interest regards the study of ion-implanted glasses and clusters.

Fabrizio Bardelli is the PHD student; his thesis concerns the study of colossal magnetoresistance materials.

Fabrizio Lamanna is the full time technician; his job regards all the aspects of the today life of the beamline.

Fabio D'Anca is a technician, working on GILDA only for a partial time (about 50%); his expertise regards mechanics and cryogenics; his contribution during the design phase is very important.

During design, building, installation and commissioning of GILDA, many groups coming from Italian University and Institutions gave a large contribution to the development of the overall GILDA project. At the moment some of them continue to contribute to the maintenance and upgrading of the beamline. Still involved are:

Frascati National Laboratory of INFN with one scientist and three technicians, mainly dedicated to the overall continuous maintenance of the beamline, its infrastructures, the REFLEXAFS apparatus and the diffraction hutch. At the moment at Frascati is under development a system for growing clusters by magnetron sputtering and rare gas aggregation.

University of Roma TRE, with two scientist, in charge of the overall project responsibility and of the maintenance, management and implementation of the diffraction hutch;

University of Trento, with three scientists and two technicians in charge of the maintenance of the EXAFS apparatus;

University of Bologna, with a scientist collaborating to many aspects of the GILDA activity.

III. Future perspectives and plans for upgrade

Future Perspectives and plans for upgrade

The future plans of the beamline are strongly dependent on the future development of the ESRF storage ring. The increase only of the current of the machine will impose some modifications to the optical elements of the beamline, in order to accommodate the higher flux, but this is in the possibility of the actual foreseen budget of the beamline. The eventual change of the source from a bending magnet into an insertion device will impose a very deep modification of all the beamline, which is out of the possibility of the actual budget.

In case of small changes of the ESRF characteristics in the next five years, the following implementations of the beamline instrumentation are foreseen.

Implementation of the optics: the beamline optics is composed of two mirrors and one monochromator. The first mirror collimates the beam minimizing its vertical divergence so maximizing the resolution of the monochromator; moreover it eliminates the higher energy part of the radiation spectrum, so minimizing the harmonic content of the outgoing beam. The second mirror focuses the beam in the different experimental apparatus. The first version of the mirror, made of three different pieces and curved by 18 piezoelectric actuators, is now being substituted by a single Si piece, curved by a single actuator. In this way we aim to minimize the vertical size of the beam, particularly important for the REFLEXAFS and diffraction apparatus.

The first mirror needs a realignment of three pieces it is made of, and this can be accomplished in the optical lab of ESRF. It will be foreseen after the installation and commissioning of the new second mirror on the basis of the results achieved on the overall beamline characteristics.

The GILDA monochromator is a prototype developed at Frascati between 1991 and 1993. It is a double crystal fixed exit monochromator, with the movements achieved by two rotations and one translation of the two crystals. The realization of the monochromator was a success that time, mainly for its unique characteristics: it sagittally focuses the beam from an initial dimension of 20mm to a final one of 1 mm. And does the focusing in a dynamical mode: the focus dimensions are kept constant during a scan of several thousands of eV.

After ten year of continuous working now the monochromator is giving some troubles; in particular after the shutdowns it shows problems in restarting; moreover the plan of the maintenance needed is not clear at all. Moreover intrinsic in the design of the monochromator itself there is no possibility to perform rapid scan as needed to implement the Quick-EXAFS" mode on the beamline. For these two reasons during the next five years the change of the monochromator with a commercial one is foreseen.

Implementation of the XAFS hutch. The enlargement of the ancillary equipments for sample conditioning is foreseen for the next five year, in particular to implement measurements at high pressure and at temperatures higher than the one nowadays available. In particular, for studies on catalysts, a new specific set-up has been studied and is under construction to monitor the structural evolution of the sample in reaction environment; this new set up gives the opportunity to warm up the sample up to 1000 °C and input different gasses necessary to study possible structural changes. Moreover, a system for studies on in-situ grown clusters is under development.

A critical point is the detection of the fluorescence. The idea is to implement the counting rate today available with the 13 Ge(hp) multidetector. Three possibilities are today under evaluation/development. The first is to buy a second Ge(hp) detector; in this way an increase of a factor of the order of two will be achieved. In addition GILDA will be no more subject to problems in case of failure of the detector as recently happened.

The second idea is the use of silicon drift detectors (SDD). Such kind of detectors, originally developed for high energy physics experiments, have been recently successfully applied to X-ray spectroscopy; they are very promising because with only moderate cooling by a single Peltier

element they reach an energy resolution (FWHM<168eV@5.9KeV) comparable to that of a liquid nitrogen cooled Ge detector; moreover due to their extremely small overall capacitance the SDDs can operate with very short shaping time and consequently at extremely high counting rate. The idea is first to test such kind of detectors on the beamline in different conditions and then, on the basis of the results and of the experience acquired, to develop a SDD crystal ball to cover a large fraction of the total solid angle.

The third idea is to increase the energy resolution of the fluorescence detector; at this purpose a collaboration with an high energy physics group of the University of Genova (Italy) is in progress, to test on the beamline Transition Edge Superconducting (TES) detectors. Such kind of detectors can have energy resolutions below the eV; some tests on a single TES detector have already been performed on GILDA¹² with encouraging results and more test are foreseen for the next future, with the goal to achieve “on the beamline” a resolution of few eV. A following step will be to implement a multidetector with only few elements (around 4) in order to study the problem of the cross talking and to increase the counting rate of a single detector. Finally, in case of success, the development of a multidetector will be evaluated.

Implementation of the Diffraction hutch. Two main implementation are foreseen; one is the use of a curved imaging plate in order to extend the detectable reciprocal space from the actual 40^0 to about 120^0 ; the use of a curved geometry will also eliminate many systematic geometrical deformations of the spectra resulting from the planar geometry of the actual detector.

The second is to implement a system with on-line capability to read the IP, like the MAR345 Image Plate detector; this will speed up the experiments, avoiding the actual dead time connected with the mounting, transport to the reader and remounting of the IP. Moreover, because the imaging plate is fixed in its position, all the errors due to the IP positioning, that actually limits the resolution achievable on the lattice parameters, will be eliminated.

¹² C. Maurizio, D. Pergolesi, F. Gatti, F. D’Acapito, M. Razeti, A. Balerna, S. Mobilio
Application of a TES micro-calorimeter as high energy resolution for hard X-rays at a synchrotron beamline”
Nuclear Instrument and Methods in Phys. Res. A **520**, 610 (2004)

IV. Scientific highlights

GILDA Scientific Highlights

Most of the research activities performed on GILDA are based on a strong collaboration between the staff group (staff at Grenoble and Italian collaborators) with the users groups. In some cases the staff group acts as expert able to optimize both the experiment and the data analysis, so maximizing the overall quality of the results obtained. In other studies the staff group act as promoter of the research itself and the collaboration with the users is mainly based on the production and characterization of the samples. Therefore it is not possible to separate the research performed by the staff from that performed in collaboration. There are also experiments fully realized by external users.

The overall activity concerns the followings main topics: semiconductors, metal clusters, magnetic materials, surface and interfaces, dopant in glasses and crystals, ion conductivity of glasses and crystals, catalysis, biophysics, earth science, archeological and cultural heritage. In addition a relevant activity concerns the study of dynamical properties and negative thermal expansion of materials; such studies analyze also the limit of the EXAFS spectroscopy itself.

Hereafter for each topic some relevant results obtained on GILDA in the period 1999-2003 are shortly presented.

Semiconductors

Ge-Si intermixing in Ge quantum dots on Si(001) and Si(111)

by F. Boscherini, G. Capellini, L. Di Gaspare, F. Rosei, N. Motta, S. Mobilio
Appl. Phys. Lett. **76**, 682 (2000)

Ge quantum dots on Si(001) are among the most studied nano-structured systems. It is known that, due to the 4.2% lattice misfit, heteroepitaxial growth proceeds with the formation of a two – dimensional wetting layer, followed by the formation of dots which relieve the lattice strain (at the cost of an increase in surface energy); this is the so – called Stranski – Krastanov growth mode. The XAS experiments performed on Ge dots formed on Si(001) and Si(111) were among the first to detect the presence of atomic intermixing, a phenomenon which had been neglected up to that time. The experimental evidence is rather clear, as can be seen in figure which compares the Ge K-edge spectra for bulk Ge, for a Ge impurity in crystalline Si and for a representative sample of Ge dots on Si(001). The asymmetrical lineshape of the first peak, which is due to the first coordination shell, indicates the presence of a significant number of Si neighbours to the average Ge atom; this indication was confirmed by a fitting of the spectra. The evolution of the intermixing process on the Si(111) surface shows an enhancement of interdiffusion with increasing substrate temperature.

Ge K-edge EXAFS spectra Ge for quantum dots on Si(001), illustrating intermixing of Si

It is now accepted that diffusion of Si atoms from the substrate reduces the strain energy associated with the heteroepitaxial growth and is a key feature of quantum dot growth. Hence, the appropriate growth mode for quantum dots is a *modified* Stranski – Krastanow one.

Bond length variation in $In_xGa_{1-x}As/InP$ strained epitaxial layers

by F. Romanato, D. De Salvador, M. Berti, A. Drigo, M. Natali, M. Tormen, G. Rossetto, S. Pascarelli, F. Boscherini, C. Lamberti, and S. Mobilio
 Phys. Rev. B, **57** 14619 (1998).

Bond length variation in $In_{0.25}Ga_{0.75}As/InP$ epitaxial layers beyond critical thickness

by M. Tormen, D. De Salvador, M. Natali, A. Drigo, F. Romanato, G. Rossetto, F. Boscherini, and S. Mobilio
 J. Appl. Phys. **86**, 2533 (1999).

Lattice distortion in $InGaAs/InP$ epitaxial films: a second and third shell XAFS study

by M. Tormen, D. de Salvador, A.V. Drigo, F. Romanato, F. Boscherini, and S. Mobilio
 Phys. Rev. B **63**, 115326 (2001)

There is a considerable interest in understanding the microscopic mechanisms of lattice misfit accommodation in epitaxial layers of semiconductor pseudobinary alloys. An understanding of the structural changes accompanying heteroepitaxial growth is necessary to model a large number of effects that strain can induce, such as band alignment in heterojunctions, structural ordering processes or structural instability governing the nucleation of defects. Basic to this problem is the local description of the degrees of freedom of the atoms inside the unit cell that must be related to the long-range description typical of the macroscopic theory of elasticity. We recall that for unstrained bulk alloys XAFS has demonstrated conclusively that the variations of the lattice parameter are accommodated at a local scale mainly by bond bending, the individual bond lengths exhibiting only a weak compositional dependence.

In a number of papers on various systems this issue has been addressed by XAFS on GILDA. The most complete data set is that reported by Romanato et al. who have studied InGaAs alloys pseudomorphically deposited on InP(001). In figure the In–As and Ga–As bond lengths are reported

In – As and Ga – As bond lengths for InGaAs/InP(001) strained epilayers and for relaxed alloys as a function of the In atomic fraction

the samples and for relaxed alloys, as a function of the In atomic fraction. Also shown are the behavior of the bond lengths in the bulk alloys as determined by Mikkelsen and Boyce (MB) and the predictions of the Virtual Crystal Approximation (VCA). It is quite clear that in the strained alloys the bond lengths actually *decrease* with increasing In concentration, the opposite of what happens in the bulk; this effect can be quantitatively understood as the effect at the local scale of the long range strain (compressive for $[\text{In}] > 0.53$, tensile for $[\text{In}] < 0.53$). The data also show that small uncertainties in the determination of bond lengths ($\sigma_R = 0.005 \text{ \AA}$) can be obtained at GILDA. In figure we also show the result of the application of the macroscopic elasticity tensor to the local scale, illustrating the good agreement with the experimental data. The curve labelled by $\xi = 0$ is obtained by neglecting differences between the force constants of the In – As and Ga – As bonds (an average value is used), while that labelled by $\xi = 1$ corresponds to using individual force constants; the two limits are indistinguishable within the experimental resolution.

The finding of direct proportionality between strain and bond length variation has been extended also to the case partially relaxed epilayers by Tormen *et al.* (1999); the same authors (Tormen *et al.* (2001)) have also quantified the changes in the second and third shell interatomic distances by using polarization – dependent measurements.

A quantitative determination of short range ordering in InGaAsN

by G. Ciatto, F. D’Acapito, L. Grenoulliet, H. Mariette, D. De Salvador, G. Bisognin, R. Carboni, L. Floreano, R. Gotter, S. Mobilio, and F. Boscherini
 Phys. Rev. B **68**, 161201(R) (2003)

The addition to III-V semiconductor alloys of small quantities of an isoelectronic impurity characterized by very different electronegativity and size with respect to the host lattice elements causes dramatic and unexpected changes in physical properties. For example, the incorporation of a low concentration of nitrogen (~0.1-1%) into GaAs, InGaAs, or GaP (the so-called “dilute nitrides”) leads to an anomalous giant decrease in the host band gap. In the quaternary alloy (InGa)(AsN) the relative disposition of cations and anions on their sublattices is not uniquely determined by the atomic concentration. In fact, in the zincblende structure each site of the anion (cation) sublattice

can be occupied by In or Ga (As or N) without any limitation. Therefore the question of the degree of atomic ordering, i.e. the relative number of each atomic bond as a function of composition, naturally arises. Specific examples of types of atomic ordering are the random case (relative number of each type of bond equal to the concentration) or short range ordering (SRO); in the relevant case of low N concentration SRO is exhibited, in the extreme cases, by a sample having only N – In or only N – Ga bonds. For (InGa)(AsN) it has been predicted [K. Kim and A. Zunger, Phys. Rev. Lett. **86**, 2609 (2001)] that precisely this type of SRO exists, with a strong preference for In – N bonds over Ga – N ones. Moreover, SRO has been predicted to cause a significant blue shift of the band gap and hence represent an intrinsic materials limitation.

Recent measurements by Ciatto *et al.* (2003) have shown that SRO does exist, but is significantly less pronounced than predicted. The figure compares the In – N coordination number

The In – N coordination number versus the N concentration in (InGa)(AsN) epilayers. Open circles are for as – deposited samples while filled circles are for annealed one.

as measured by In – edge XAFS with the N concentration measured by Nuclear Reaction Analysis. As – deposited samples (open circles) exhibit a random atomic arrangement, while annealed samples show a statistically significant deviation towards SRO. The degree of SRO falls short of the maximum possible and of that predicted (diamond in the figure).

Metal Clusters

Co dimers observed by extended X-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy

by G. Faraci, A.R. Pennisi, A. Balerna, H. Pattyn, G. Koops, G. Zhang
Physical Review Letters, Vol. 86 pp. 3566-3569 (2001)

Clusters of magnetic elements exhibit very exciting properties in the frontier field of nanostructures. Of particular interest is the distinction between interior and interface contributions of large agglomerates embedded into a matrix. In order to confine small Co clusters in a silver matrix, cobalt was implanted at 50 keV in an Ag layer 50 nm thick, grown by molecular beam epitaxy (MBE), with a homogeneous concentration of 0.1 at%. Other methods were also used such as MBE co-evaporation of Ag and Co, and Co implantation during the silver layer growth, for dilutions up to 6 at%. The samples were observed at several temperatures (77, 125, 175, 225 K) by the XAFS technique at GILDA to investigate the local configuration around a Co absorber. The spectra, analysed by standard methods, clearly showed first, second, and third coordination shells around Co, with Co and Ag features very well resolved in each shell. From the coordination number and distance of each contribution we can easily deduce several important conclusions about the local

aggregation of cobalt. Depending on the dilution and on the thermal treatment different scenarios can be drawn: the first is concerned with the presence of Co dimers slightly contracted in the matrix in quasi substitutional configuration in the fcc silver lattice; they appear in a chainlike order with each dimer at 90° from each other, along opposite square faces of the silver lattice. This result was obtained for the as-prepared sample at low dilution. At higher concentration small cobalt clusters as Co₈ at 6 at% (co-evaporated sample) and Co₂₀ at 1.9 at% (implanted sample) were detected.

A possible configuration of 4 Co dimers in quasi substitutional positions in the silver fcc lattice. The dimers, contracted and disposed orthogonally to each other, form a kind of rotating chain on parallel square faces.

After suitable thermal treatment larger clusters can grow: we observed in fact Co₈₀ and Co₁₃₆ agglomerates. Here, the separation of the interface bonds from the homoatomic interactions is particularly valuable. The evolution of the raw absorption spectra in the near edge region demonstrates another interesting feature shown in figure. A clear phase transition is visible from the comparison of the shape and features of a hcp Co foil with respect to the nanoaggregates and to the dimers. Whereas the spectrum of the largest Co cluster looks very similar to the Co foil spectrum, the dimers, in the fcc configuration of the silver lattice, present strongly shifted features, showing evidence of a fcc → hcp phase transition as the number of atoms/cluster is larger than about 100.

Near-edge structure of the spectra showing dramatic modifications in the threshold features, clearly shifted with respect to the reference Co foil

Furthermore, the gradual evolution, as the size of the clusters increases, towards the bulk cobalt structure could indicate the presence of fcc/hcp stacking faults and/or a combination of hcp clusters with a more diluted cobalt in Ag precursor stage. Finally, we point out that the vibrational behaviour of each configuration vs. temperature permitted the determination of the Debye temperature; we mention only the higher hardness of the Co-Co dimer bond with respect to Co-Ag, and the Debye temperature (200 K) of the interface bonds Co-Ag for the largest clusters.

Magnetic Materials

Temperature dependence of non-Debye disorder in doped manganites

by C. Meneghini, R. Cimino, S. Pascarelli, S. Mobilio, C. Raghu, D.D. Sarma
Phys. Rev. **B56** 3520 (1997)

Local structure of hole doped manganites: influence of temperature and applied magnetic field

by C. Meneghini, C. Castellano, S. Mobilio, A. Kumar, S. Ray, D.D. Sarma
Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter, **14**, 1967 (2002)

Mixed valence manganese oxide perovskites with the general formula $A_{1-x}B_xMnO_3$ (where A is a rare earth ion and B a divalent metal) have been the subject of intensive theoretical and experimental investigations due to their remarkable magneto-transport properties resulting from a delicate and complex interplay among electronic, magnetic and structural degree of freedom. For a range of compositions, these compounds are ferromagnetic metals at low temperatures and become paramagnetic insulators at high temperatures. Some compounds, like $La_{1-x}Ca_xMnO_3$ with $0.2 < x < 0.5$, have the metal to insulator (MI) transition temperature (T_{MI}) close and coupled to the Curie temperature (T_c), producing a characteristic sharp resistivity drop on cooling below T_c . The application of an external magnetic field strongly enhances the electrical conductivity near the transition producing the so-called colossal magnetoresistance effect (CMR). The theories proposed to interpret the CMR, relies on the competition between the double exchange mechanism, favouring the ferromagnetic metallic state, and an electron-phonon coupling reducing the charge mobility in the high temperature insulating phase. As a matter of fact the size and strength of polaronic distortions are the key points in the discussion: in the limit of strong coupling, associated in the literature with the formation of small polarons, the charge carriers are localized on the locally distorted sites, thus the conductivity is given by the thermally activated hopping or tunnelling between distorted sites. The other limit of weak coupling is associated with the formation of large polarons extending over a wide spatial range and having an itinerant character. Local structure studies (neutron scattering, Mn-K edge XAS) provided evidence for the evolution from a strong-coupling insulating phase ($T > T_{MI}$) to a metallic phase ($T < T_{MI}$). In this scenario the mechanism through which an applied magnetic field (H) promotes the conductivity seems limited to the spin-charge coupling as described by the double exchange theory.

The results of accurate Mn K-edge XAFS studies on $La_{1-x}Ca_xMnO_3$, as a function of composition

Magnetotransport properties and structural results on $La_{1-x}Ca_xMnO_3$: on the left the resistivity (upper panels) trend as a function of temperature and magnetic field (dots) is compared with the evolution of Mn-O bond lengths as a function of T and H. On the right the variance of Mn-O bond length distribution (d_{JT}) is shown (upper panels).

The lower panes compare the MR effect with the relative variation of Debye Waller factors (see text).

($x=0.25, 0.33$), temperature (77-350 K) and magnetic field ($H=0, 1.1\text{T}$) performed on GILDA (see figure) unambiguously pointed out the increase in electron-phonon interaction in the insulating phase. These results definitively proved that relatively large local distortions on MnO_6 remain in the ferromagnetic metallic phase, reaching the 50 % of that found in fully distorted LnMnO_3 , in contrast with the models envisaging the complete vanishing of Jahn-Teller distortions in the ferromagnetic metallic phase. This finding definitively confirms the transition from a single site strong coupling regime (small polarons), to an intermediate coupling regime in which weaker distortions of MnO_6 octahedra are spread over few neighbour sites (large polarons).

The second relevant finding can be derived comparing the magnetoresistance (MR) effect with the relative variation of Debye-Waller factors ($\Delta\sigma^2$) with the magnetic field (see figure):

$$\text{MR} = (\mathbf{R}_{(H=0)} - \mathbf{R}_{(H=1.1)}) / \mathbf{R}_{(H=0)} \quad \Delta\sigma^2 = (\sigma_{(H=0)}^2 - \sigma_{(H=1.1)}^2) / \sigma_{(H=0)}^2$$

The quantity $\Delta\sigma^2$ should be considered as the microscopic structural counterpart of the magnetoresistance effect.

The observed effect cannot be explained assuming that the applied magnetic field only enhances the charge hopping through the double exchange mechanism, without the participation of the lattice; it implies in fact, that the magnetic field also reduces the structural distortions through a softening of the electron-lattice coupling.

Microstructural and magnetic evolution upon annealing of giant magnetoresistance melt-spun Co-Cu granular alloys

by A. García-Prieto, M. L. Fdez-Gubieda, C. Meneghini, A. García-Arribas
Phys. Rev. B **67**, 224415 (2003)

Granular magnetic alloys are made of magnetic nanoclusters embedded in non-magnetic (metallic or insulating) matrixes. These materials show peculiar magnetic and magnetotransport properties such as super-paramagnetism and giant magnetoresistance (GMR), which are interesting both for applicative purposes and for fundamental research in the field of nano structured materials. GMR phenomena in granular alloys arises from the spin dependent scattering at the interfaces between the magnetic granules and the matrix. The small size of magnetic particles and the sharp interfaces are the main factors determining magnetoresistance properties.

Granular Co-Cu systems (g-Co-Cu) present GMR. Co and Cu are immiscible elements at room temperature but metastable solid solutions of Co-Cu can be prepared by non equilibrium systems like rapid quenching, laser ablation and so on. Suitable thermal treatments allow optimising the MR effect. A peculiar aspect of g- $\text{Co}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}$ alloys is that, in a wide range of composition ($0.05 \leq x \leq 0.2$) and despite the preparation method (rapid quenching or laser ablation), the MR effect is maximized by thermal treatment at a temperature of about 450°C . The physical origin of this finding was clarified combining complementary structural techniques like high-resolution x-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) with magnetic measurements (MR and hysteresis loops). The structure of g-alloys appears to be made of three phases: a Cu rich non magnetic phase, a Co-rich ferromagnetic phase (FM) made of large Co clusters (~ 10 nm or more) and a superparamagnetic phase (SPM) made of small (nm size) Co clusters which are the responsible of GMR effect. The thermal treatments affect the GMR by changing the relative proportions of these phases. This picture was achieved thanks to the different properties of the used experimental techniques. XRD, detecting long-range order structural properties (~ 10 nm scale), was able to probe Cu-rich phases and large Co-rich clusters (FM). The hysteresis loops analysis allowed to quantify the fraction of Co in the FM (large Co clusters) and SPM (small Co Clusters) phases. Finally the XAS technique probes in details the average Co local structure in the sample in every phase. This allowed to clearly understand the micro-structural modifications induced by thermal annealing and to relate them to the evolution of GMR. The as quenched samples, before annealing, contain the majority of Co in SPM clusters coexisting with a minor percentage of Co diluted in the Cu rich matrix or condensed in ferromagnetic clusters. Thermal treatment induces the segregation

of Co atoms: raising the annealing temperature till 550°C the percentage of diluted Co diminishes on behalf of the SPM phase with the FM phase fraction remaining unchanged. Above 550°C the fraction of SPM phase decreases on the behalf of FM phase. This deep knowledge of the microstructure at each annealing stage allowed to experimentally show that the main factors leading to the optimal GMR response in CoCu are: the surface to volume ratio (small particles), the SPM particle concentration and the sharpness of the interfaces. The consequences of thermal annealing can be summarized as follows: up to 400°C the annealing process engenders the precipitation of SPM clusters and reduces the interface sharpness. These factors enlarge the MR. Above 450°C the SPM cluster size and interparticle distance increases (figure), at the same time the interfaces of small Co granules roughens due to Cu – Co interdiffusion. The combination of all these effects abruptly depresses the GMR.

The GMR effect reaches the maximum value after annealing at 450°C despite the sample composition (upper panel). The drop of GMR is related to the creasing of interparticle distance(lower panel).

Surface and Interfaces

Oxide/metal interface distance and epitaxial strain in the NiO/Ag(001) system

by C. Lamberti, E. Groppo, C. Prestipino, S. Casassa, A.M. Ferrari, C. Pisani, C. Giovanardi, P. Luches, S. Valeri, and F. Boscherini
 Phys. Rev. Lett. **91**, 046101 (2003)

In recent years, the physical properties of two dimensional metal-oxide epilayers on metal substrates have become a topic of great interest. Films a few monolayers (ML) thick can be deposited epitaxially on metal substrates by ultrahigh vacuum techniques, yielding reproducible and well-characterized systems. It has been shown that the energy gap of the oxide, in the oxide/metal system, can be modulated by the film thickness T . The demonstrated ability to control T represents therefore a new technological opportunity for band-gap engineering. It has also been argued that the presence of the metal substrate can alter significantly the electronic structure of the oxide and

influence its chemical properties, with a prospective range of important applications. In the latter respect, *ab initio* simulations of perfect oxide/metal epilayers have given so far a different indication; namely, the electronic structure of the oxide is modified only in a strict vicinity of the interface. The question has therefore been raised whether residual film defectivity could be responsible for the observed enhancement of chemical activity and other evidence of modified electronic structure; in this case a perfectly epitaxial overlayer would be a poor model of the real systems. In order to provide an accurate estimate of the geometry of the NiO/Ag(001) interface the authors performed a polarization – dependent XAFS investigation, and compared their result with that of electron diffraction techniques and *ab – initio* simulations. In the figure the Ni K – edge XAFS data for 3 ML NiO/Ag(001), taken with the electric vector perpendicular and parallel to the interface are shown.

Ni K – edge XAFS data and corresponding fits for 3 ML NiO/Ag(001). Top and bottom curves: electric vector parallel and perpendicular to the interface, respectively. The shaded area has been excluded by the fits

The data analysis shows the absence of significant interdiffusion and shows that the 3 ML epilayer is pseudomorphically distorted with the in – plane lattice parameter equal to that of the substrate; an interface Ni – Ag signal was detected which is compatible with the growth of the epilayer with O on top of Ag and an interface distance which is expanded compared to both the Ag and NiO lattice parameters.

Dopant in glasses and crystals

Local environment of rare-earth dopants in silica–titania–alumina glasses: An extended x-ray absorption fine structure study at the K edges of Er and Yb

by F. d'Acapito, S.Mobilio, L.Santos, R.M.Almeida
Appl. Phys. Lett. **78** (2001), 2676.

The development of new luminescent materials represents a major issue in the field of optical devices for signal processing. The former systems are usually based on glassy matrices doped with Rare Earth (RE) whose emission lines in the infrared region are as near as possible to the absorption minima of the matrix. Rare earth ions as Er, Pr and Yb are suitable candidates for the silica-based optic fibers. Because the luminescent properties strongly depend on the local chemical order or chemical state of the doping agent a selective local probe like Extended X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (EXAFS) is extremely powerful in studying such materials.

In silicate and phosphate glasses, a detailed description of the Er and Yb sites has been given by an extensive study performed on GILDA. The data analysis was performed using the Multiple Scattering (MS) formalism to interpret the signals. In this way, a link of RE to the non-bonding oxygens in the polyhedra (SiO_4 or PO_4) constituting the glassy matrix has been evidenced, as well as a well defined RE-O-Si(or P) bonding angle, around 135 deg. No evolution of the site with the RE concentration from below to above the luminescence concentration quenching value has been observed and in particular no evidence of RE-RE coordination has been found in all cases studied. The absence of visible RE-RE coordination is of paramount importance in the interpretation of the phenomenon of luminescence lifetime shortening upon increase of the concentration (luminescence quenching phenomenon) that was previously attributed to the formation of direct RE-RE bonds in the matrix. On the other hand, by studying Silica-titania-alumina glasses a preferential coordination of Er with Al in second shell was found in agreement with other studies on similar systems. In order to obtain a stringent determination of the RE local site an experiment at the RE K edges ($\text{Er}_K = 57486 \text{ eV}$, $\text{Yb}_K = 61332 \text{ eV}$) was carried out. In this way, by avoiding the interference of neighboring L edges, we had access to high values of the photoelectron wavevector k necessary to well evidence the RE-RE coordination. The experiments ruled out the occurrence of RE-RE coordination and provided the basis of an original model for RE clustering in glasses that accounts for the approaching of the RE ions and the absence of RE-RE coordination observed in EXAFS data.

Data at the Er K edge on Er doped sol-gel glasses. The inset shows the clustering model proposed.

Evolution of local environment around Er upon thermal annealing in Er and O co-implanted Si

by A. Terrasi, G. Franzò, S. Coffa, F. Priolo, F. D'Acapito, and S. Mobilio

Appl. Phys. Lett. **70**, 1712 (1997)

EXAFS analysis of Er sites in Er-O and Er-F co-doped crystalline Si

O'Hare T.; Rittenberg M.B.; Terrasi A.; Priolo F.; Franzo G.; Coffa S.; D'Acapito F.; Mobilio S.

J. Lumin. **80** (1999) 363.

The possibility of achieving luminescence at $1.54 \mu\text{m}$ in Silicon by the intentional addition of a relatively low concentration of Er atoms to the lattice has attracted considerable interest and research in Silicon technology. XAS has been important in elucidating the relation between the

local structure of Er and the luminescence efficiency. It is known [D.L. Adler et al., Appl. Phys. Lett. **61**, 2181 (1992)] that a high luminescence efficiency is obtained only when Er is at the center of a distorted octahedron composed by oxygen atoms and not bonded to Si as in ErSi₂; in the former geometry the dipole – forbidden *f*–*f* transitions at 1.54 μm are more efficient than in the latter.

Due to the fact that the equilibrium concentration of substitutional Er in Si is well below the minimum needed for device applications and that the formation of Er silicide leads to poorly luminescent sites, many efforts were dedicated to develop preparation methods overcoming the limit of the low solid solubility of Er in Si and guaranteeing an high degree of Er – O bonding. The co-doping of Er ions with O ions followed by appropriate thermal treatments revealed to be efficient to obtain good optical properties.

The local structure around Er was studied in Si samples coimplanted with Er and O atoms; a concentration as high as 10¹⁹ Er atoms/cm³ was achieved. This study extended previous XAS investigations to technologically relevant systems, clarifying the structural modification induced by thermal treatment. In the as implanted samples, Er forms silicide phases, with no detectable Er - O coordination; Er – O coordination is absent also in samples annealed only at low temperature (400 °C). On the other hand samples annealed at a temperature of 620 °C or higher exhibit a local structure in which Er is in fact bonded to O (see figure).

Evolution of the Er environment upon annealing in Er + O implanted Si

A similar behaviour was evidenced also for Er + F doped samples. A detailed analysis of these data in the MS formalism has permitted to describe in detail the site of Er + O clusters in Si that exhibits a well defined Er-O and bond length as well as a well defined Er-O-Si bond angle similarly to what observed in glasses. These experimental data rule out the occurrence of Er in tetrahedral interstitial T_i or substitutional T_s sites described in a number of with previous theoretical calculations and are compatible with the positioning of Er ions in O-decorated the hexagonal interstitial H_i sites.

Negative thermal expansion

Local Thermal Expansion in a Cuprite Structure: The Case of Ag₂O

by S. a Beccara, G. Dalba, P. Fornasini, R. Grisenti, A. Sanson, and F. Rocca
Phys. Rev. Lett. 89 (2002) 25503

In many systems, negative thermal expansion (NTE) is observed in temperature ranges of different extent, and can be attributed to geometrical effects of low-frequency vibrations perpendicular to some inter-atomic links: guitar string effect in simple crystals with diamond or zinc-blende structure, rigid unit modes (RUM) in framework structures, etc. These vibrations induce an overall contraction, which opposes and sometimes overcomes the positive expansion due to the potential anharmonicity. The possibility of measuring the real expansion of selected bonds and the perpendicular MSRD, offered by EXAFS, represents an effective tool for directly monitoring the local behaviour of NTE materials, complementary to Bragg diffraction and alternative to the less accurate and less simple analysis of thermal diffuse scattering in total scattering experiments.

Such studies require extremely accurate measurements as a function of the temperature and very sophisticated and suitable interpretation schemes. The analysis of the *1st coordination shell* signal can generally be done within the single scattering approximation using the ratio method to obtain accurate relative values of EXAFS cumulants. The analysis of the *outer coordination shells* is by far more complicated, owing to the difficulty of disentangling their single contributions and to the effects of multiple scattering; a purely phenomenological analysis is generally inaccurate, and one has to resort to simulation and non-linear fitting procedures.

Significant results have been obtained with measurements performed on GILDA on Cu₂O and Ag₂O, two crystals sharing the same framework structure, formed by two independent and interpenetrating networks of M₄O tetrahedra (M=Cu, Ag), and affected by macroscopic NTE over extended temperature intervals. For a deep understanding of the problem, an extensive and extremely accurate study at the Ag K edge was performed in Ag₂O in the temperature range 7 to 500 K. Results show that the 2nd-shell Ag-Ag distance decreases at increasing temperature, in qualitative agreement with the negative thermal expansion (NTE) measured by diffraction. On the contrary, the 1st-shell Ag-O distance neatly increases. The first-shell perpendicular MSRD is much larger than the parallel MSRD, and comparable with the 2nd-shell parallel MSRD, confirming that the NTE is connected to vibrations perpendicular to the O-Ag-O chain, but also suggesting the inadequacy of models solely based on rigid unit modes.

An additional set of measurements was done in the range 4 to 100 K at much closely spaced temperature steps, to investigate on a phase transition observed below 40 K by diffraction. The phase transition is clearly evidenced also in EXAFS spectra; its structural interpretation is under way. The good quality of data allowed to refine the 2nd-shell analysis from 40 to 100 K. Actually, the 12 Ag atoms composing the 2nd shell can be grouped into two sets: 6 atoms are connected to the central Ag atom via an oxygen atom, and belong to the same network of tetrahedra (Type A); the other 6 Ag atoms belong to the other network (Type B). EXAFS shows that the Type A distance decreases, while Type B distance increases when temperature increases.

In a further investigation performed on Cu₂O similar results were obtained, although both positive and negative expansions are much weaker. In any case, negative and positive expansions are found for Type A and Type B 2nd-shell distances also in Cu₂O.

Catalysis

Homoleptic Cu^I(CO)₃ Cations in Cu^I-exchanged ZSM-5: a XAFS Study

by C. Lamberti, G. Turnes Palomino, S. Bordiga, G. Berlier, A. Zecchina and F. D'Acapito
Angew. Chem. Int. Ed., **39**, 2138 (2000)

Zeolites are nanoporous crystalline aluminosilicates constituted by corner-sharing [TO₄] tetrahedra, where T represents a silicon or an aluminum atom, with chemical composition described by the general formula Mⁿ⁺_{x/n}[(AlO₂)_x(SiO₂)_y]^x. The introduction of a trivalent Al(III) atom in a [TO₄] unit (substituting the tetravalent Si(IV) atom), induces a net negative charge into the zeolitic framework

(x-) which must be compensated by the presence of charge-balancing extra-framework cations ($M^{n+}_{x/n}$). Such cations can act as active centres in acid-catalysed reactions ($M^+ = H^+$) or in redox reactions ($M^{n+} =$ a transition metal ion).

Cu-exchanged zeolites have recently attracted great interest as catalysts for the direct conversion of NO into N_2 and O_2 and for the selective reduction of NO with ammonia and hydrocarbons. A thorough characterisation of these catalysts needs (i) the structural localisation of the active centres, (ii) the study of the reactivity of Cu(I) ions by the interaction with probe molecules like CO or NO, and (iii) the monitoring of the complete Cu(I) \rightleftharpoons Cu(II) reduction/oxidation cycle. Point (iii) has been investigated using EPR, IR, UV-Vis, XPS and XANES experiments.

The siting of copper ions in Cu(I)-Y zeolite, prepared by gas-phase exchange of H-Y with CuCl, has been investigated employing EXAFS data collected *in situ* at the beamline GILDA and X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) collected at BM16. The Rietveld refinement of the XRPD data of the zeolite *in vacuo* shows that 23.4(2) cuprous ions are located at site I*, 6.1(3) at site II, and 11.5(3) at site II* (see top part of figure). From the XRPD study the occupancy-weighted EXAFS signal expected for the three families of Cu(I) sites, exhibiting 3 equivalent oxygen atoms at 2.00 Å, 2.03 Å and 2.21 Å, respectively were determined. The results obtained from the one-shell fit of the EXAFS signal obtained by adding the contribution from the three families (bottom spectrum in Figure 21) were in full agreement with the one-shell fit of the experimental EXAFS signal.

As for point (ii), the results obtained from synchrotron radiation techniques are supported by parallel microcalorimetry and FTIR studies of adsorbed CO. From the combined use of the three techniques we learn that CO is adsorbed on the Cu(I)-zeolites at ambient temperature with the formation of Cu(I)(CO) adducts, which evolve into Cu(I)(CO)₂ upon increasing the CO pressure (P_{CO}). At 80 K, and low P_{CO} , FTIR indicates that two types of monocarbonyl species are observed in Cu(I)-Y, corresponding to CO adsorbed on copper ions located at sites II and II*. On increasing P_{CO} , and subsequent formation of polycarbonylic species, cations at site II* move to the more-exposed position II and only a kind of Cu(I)(CO)₂ adduct is observed by FTIR, in full agreement with the XRPD data (bottom part of Figure).

Template burning inside TS-1 and Fe-MFI molecular sieves: An *in situ* XRPD study

by M. Milanesio, G. Artioli, A.F. Gualtieri, L. Palin, C. Lamberti

Journal of the American Chemical Society 125 (2003) 14549-14558

The high X-ray flux available at the ESRF, combined with the use of a suitably designed area detector setup available on the GILDA BM8 beamline allowed Milanesio et al. to follow in real time by XRPD the structural changes occurring during the template burning processes inside TS-1 and Fe-MFI zeolites (see Figure part a). The Rietveld full structure analysis yields the template occupancy factor vs. T (full line, left axis) in good agreement with the thermo-gravimetric data (Figure part b, solid squares, right axis). The model for the refinement of the template molecule derives from the single crystal XRD study performed on ID11 beamline [Palin, et al. *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 107 (2003) 4034].

(a): Evolution of the XRPD patterns in the $2.5\text{--}12.5^\circ$ 2θ -interval (corresponding to $14.2\text{--}2.8 \text{ \AA}$ d-spacing) as a function of the temperature during the *in situ* template burning of TS-1, $\lambda = 0.82667(6) \text{ \AA}$. Main reflections have been indicated.

(b) Direct comparison between the refined TPA^+ occupancy factor (scattered red squares, right axis) and the per cent loss of weight (continuous blue line, left axis) during the template burning process inside TS-1. Adapted from Milanesio, et al. *JACS* 125 (2003) 14549; *ESRF Highlights* 125 (2003) 113.

By monitoring the evolution of the a , b and c cell axes vs. temperature (Figure) it has been observed that the volume changes anisotropically during the whole process, for both TS-1 and Fe-MFI, following the inequalities $b(T)/b_0 < c(T)/c_0 \ll a(T)/a_0$, being a_0 , b_0 and c_0 the starting lattice parameters. These results imply that the zeolite crystals are subject to remarkable stress forces

Evolution of the cell volume (a) and the lattice parameters for both TS-1 (b) and Fe-MFI (c) during the in situ template burning in the 300-1000 K range plotted as $V(T)/V_0$, $a(T)/a_0$, $b(T)/b_0$, and $c(T)/c_0$ (being the reference values obtained at 350 and 340 K for TS-1 and Fe-MFI, respectively). Reproduced from Milanesio, et al. JACS 125 (2003) 14549.

during the process, and that the strong anisotropic contraction contributes to crack formation in the zeolite crystals. These data allow us to have, for the first time, a complete view of the structural rearrangements induced by the template burning process on the zeolitic framework. Isothermal runs have also been performed, and the results of the kinetic analysis indicated that the template burning is a diffusion limited reaction with monodimensional advancement. The rate limiting step of the reaction is the diffusion of the volatile products of the template burning out of the crystal. Chemical and steric considerations indicate that the straight channels along the b axis are the more favorable direction for the molecule diffusion and removal. Corresponding Arrhenius plots result in an apparent activation energy values of $151 \pm 11 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$ and of $159 \pm 7 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$ for TS-1 and Fe-MFI, respectively.

Biophysics

Microarchitectural and Physical Changes During Fetal Growth in Human Vertebral Bone

by S. Nuzzo, C. Meneghini, P. Braillon, R. Bouvier, S. Mobilio, F Peyrin

Journal of Bone and Mineral Research 18, 760 (2003)

Rietveld Refinement on X-Ray Diffraction Patterns of Bioapatite in Human Fetal Bones

by C. Meneghini, M. C. Dalconi, S. Nuzzo, S. Mobilio, R. H. Wenk

Biophysical Journal 84, 2021-2029 (2003)

Bioapatite, the main constituent of mineralised tissue in mammalian bone, is a calcium-phosphate based mineral whose structure and composition is close to hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$). The crystallographic structure of bioapatite has been studied by x-ray powder diffraction (XRD) and x-ray microdiffraction (μ -XRD) in order to assess the bioapatite microstructural changes as a function of foetal age and in a single bone trabecula. These studies are complemented by architectural characterization made by x-ray computed microtomography. Bone can be considered as a dispersion of mineral particles (biomineral) embedded in an organic matrix, which form the contiguous phase. Bioapatite, the main constituent of mammalian bone, has variable composition due to the biochemical activity, age, physiologic state, body health and so on. These characteristics make difficult to univocally establish the composition and structure of bone. In addition natural bioapatite presents a highly defective/ poorly crystallized structure and this prevents the accurate phase determination by standard XRD techniques. Even more complex is the definitive assessment of bone structure during the early stages of bone formation, at foetal stage. On the other hand these are fundamental issues to definitively understand the structural and chemical mechanism leading to the formation of new bone and the influence of physiological and environmental constraints.

In this work the capabilities of synchrotron radiation XRD were fully exploited in order to give the first systematic characterization of human bone mineral structure during the early stage of bone formation (ossification processes). Twenty-two vertebral bone samples were collected from healthy human foeti at different gestation ages (16-26 weeks). Powder diffraction patterns were collected using the Imaging Plate set-up on the GILDA beamline, which allows to collect high statistics and good resolution diffraction patterns using reduced collection times (5 min/pattern). One of the samples (26 week old) has been also studied by μ -XRD (ESRF-ID13 beamline). In this case the small beam size allows an accurate XRD mapping of a single bone trabecula selectively probing the surface and bulk regions. Rietveld refinement of XRD patterns gives the bioapatite crystallographic structure while the peak shape analysis gave the crystallite size. The main results are summarized in figure.

Particle size (τ_c) and c-axis compressive strain (c/a) detected by XRD and μ -XRD.

The XRD study shows the growth of the bioapatite crystallites as a function of the foetal age. Moreover the younger bone bioapatite cell is compressed along the c-axis, with respect to the synthetic hydroxyapatite, while the compressive strain decreases as a function of foetal age. The fine mapping available through μ -XRD shows that the bioapatite at the trabecula surface, which is made of immature early-formed bone tissue, presents smaller crystallites and larger compressive strain with respect to the bulk bioapatite where mature bioapatite crystals are larger and the compressive strain decreases. These results suggest that the compressive strain observed is an intrinsic feature related more to the bioapatite crystal maturation process than to the foetal age.

Archeological and cultural heritage

Copper in glazes of Renaissance lustre pottery: Nanoparticles, ions and local environment

by Padovani S., Sada C., Mazzoldi P., Brunetti B., Borgia I., Sgamellotti A., Giulivi A., D'Acapito F., Battaglin G.

J.Appl. Phys. 93, 10058-10063, 2003

Silver and copper nanoclusters in the lustre decoration of Italian Renaissance pottery: an EXAFS study

by Padovani S., Borgia I., Brunetti B., Sgamellotti A., Giulivi A., D'Acapito F., Mazzoldi P., Sada C., Battaglin G.,

Applied Physics A, 79, 229-233, 2004

Metal-glass nanocomposites, formed by nanometer-sized crystalline metal clusters embedded in a glass matrix, are characterized by specific optical and magnetic properties. In particular, due to the third order optical nonlinearities, they are of current interest in the development of glass-based devices for optoelectronics. It has been recently found that lustre decorations, typical of the Medieval and Renaissance pottery of the Mediterranean basin, substantially consist of a metal-glass nanocomposite thin layer. Indeed, by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) it has been shown that lustre consists of a thin film composed of a heterogeneous

distribution of silver and copper nanoparticles of sizes ranging from 5 to 100 nm. These decorations show peculiar optical properties, producing brilliant reflections of different colors, iridescent effects, and iridescence. In spite of the large historical documentation, only little scientific information on luster is available. Luster chromatic effects are expected to depend on the properties of the nanoparticle colloidal dispersion. However, luster optical properties may also be influenced by the presence of ionic copper in the glaze because, when present in specific oxidation, it could modify the glaze refraction index or even contribute directly to its coloration. In addition, copper ions can play a relevant role in the luster formation mechanism. To investigate the presence of nanoparticles and of copper ions in the luster glaze and to determine copper ion states and their local order, a study has been performed on the original samples of Umbrian Renaissance luster pottery exclusively by nondestructive techniques, among which XAFS.

Elemental analyses indicate that silver and copper are present in gold decorations, while copper only is present in red decorations. The chromatic effects are determined by the fraction of metal ions reduced to nanoparticles. Specifically, silver nanoparticles determine the gold colour, while the red colour is determined by nanoparticles of copper. EXAFS measurements, carried out at the Cu and Ag *K* edge, indicate that in both gold and red luster copper is mostly in the oxidized form (Cu⁺ and Cu²⁺) with a large prevalence of Cu⁺. States and local environment of copper ions are similar to those found in copper–alkali ion-exchanged silicate glass samples. This strongly supports the view that luster formation is mediated by a copper– and silver–alkali ion exchange as a first step, followed by nucleation and growth of metal nanoparticles.

The red luster has also been studied by EXAFS measurements carried out in the total yield mode, to probe only the first 150 nm of the glaze layer. These data indicated that in some cases luster nanoclusters may be confined in a very thin layer close to the surface.

Ag *K*-edge EXAFS data recorded on gold luster suggest the presence of both metallic and oxidized silver. The presence of silver nanoparticles is confirmed by the fact that silver coordinates about eight silver atoms at a distance of 2.88 ± 0.02 Å.

This study was described in the Science Update section of Nature published on June the 30th 2003.

V. Selection of five publications

Selection of reprints

The following are five selected papers of work accomplished on GILDA beamline.

C. Lamberti, G. Turnes Palomino, S. Bordiga, G. Berlier, A. Zecchina and F. D'Acapito
“Homoleptic $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{CO})_3$ Cations in Cu^{I} -exchanged ZSM-5: a XAFS Study”
Angew. Chem. Int. Ed., **39**, 2138 (2000)

G. Faraci, A.R. Pennisi, A. Balerna, H. Pattyn, G. Koops, G. Zhang
“Co dimers observed by EXAFS spectroscopy”
Phys. Rev. Lett. **86**, 3566 (2001)

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Overview of the Scientific Activity performed on the GILDA beamline

The overall scientific activity concerns the followings main topics: semiconductors, metal clusters, magnetic materials, surface and interfaces, dopant in glasses and crystals, the structure of glasses, catalysis, biophysics, earth science, archeological and cultural heritage. In addition a relevant activity was dedicated to the study of dynamical properties and negative thermal expansion of materials; such studies analyzed also the limit of the EXAFS spectroscopy itself, in determining interatomic distances.

Hereafter a brief overview of the research performed on GILDA since the beginning of its activity is reported. No attempt to citing *all* papers reporting works performed at GILDA has been made, but we believe that the most significant ones are described and quoted.

Semiconductor research at GILDA

Since the GILDA beamline was open to users, research on semiconductors has been an area of significant activity, both in terms of requested beamtime and in terms of the quantity and quality of publications. This is due to the existence of a strong tradition in semiconductor research in the Italian community and to the specific instrumentation that is available on GILDA. In particular:

- i) dynamical sagittal focusing¹ on the fixed exit monochromator provides a high brilliance photon beam on the sample, indispensable for most of the experiments here reported;
- ii) the thirteen – element HP-Ge fluorescence detector with related digital electronics² has allowed high quality measurements on dopants and epilayers;
- iii) the sample holder geometry, including a vibrating LNT cooled sample holder³, has allowed polarization - dependent measurements on oriented crystalline wafers;
- iv) more recently, the construction of a grazing – incidence X-ray absorption station⁴ has allowed investigations of the near – surface region of semiconductor samples.

Nanostructures

The possibility of altering the physical properties of semiconductors by exploiting quantum size effects has lead to the great recent interest in nanostructures. In this field, XAS has the advantage of providing a local view of the structure thus providing rather direct information on intermixing and bond length strain. At GILDA studies have been performed both on self-assembled quantum dots and wires and on nanostructures formed using ion implantation.

Ge quantum dots on Si(001) are among the most studied systems. It is known that, due to the 4.2% lattice misfit, heteroepitaxial growth proceeds with the formation of a two – dimensional wetting layer, followed by the formation of dots which relieve the lattice strain (at the cost of an increase in surface energy); this is the so – called Stranski – Krastanov growth mode. The XAS experiments performed on Ge dots formed on Si(001) and Si(111)⁵ were among the first to detect the presence of atomic intermixing, a phenomenon which had been neglected up to that time. The experimental evidence is rather clear, as can be seen in figure n. 1 which compares the Ge K-edge spectra for bulk Ge, for a Ge impurity in crystalline Si and for a representative sample of Ge dots on Si(001). The asymmetrical lineshape of the first peak, which is due to the first coordination shell, indicates the presence of a significant number of Si neighbors to the average Ge atom; this indication has been confirmed by a fitting of the spectra. It is now accepted that diffusion of Si atoms from the substrate reduces the strain energy associated with the heteroepitaxial growth and is a key feature of quantum dot growth. Hence, the appropriate growth mode for quantum dots is a *modified* Stranski – Krastanow one. The same group⁶ has also monitored the evolution of the intermixing process on the Si(111) surface, finding an enhancement of interdiffusion with

increasing substrate temperature. Finally we mention that Kovats *et al.* (Phys. Rev. B **62**, 8223 (2000)) found that intermixing was inhibited by the saturation of the dangling bonds on the Si(111) surface by B atoms.

Atomic intermixing is not limited to the Ge/Si system but was found also in compound semiconductors. Galluppi *et al.*⁷ were the first to detect In/Ga intermixing in nominally pure InAs dots on GaAs by In K-edge XAS; these structural measurements were correlated to photoluminescence investigation of the optical properties. D'Acapito *et al.*⁸ confirmed this result in a grazing incidence measurement on 1.3 to 3 monolayer (ML) thick samples and discussed the values of the bond lengths, finding that their value could provide reliable information on the state of strain of the dots. Finally, Renevier *et al.*⁹ contrasted the case of InAs/GaAs dots to that of InAs/InP quantum wires; in the former case the authors confirmed the previously cited results while no interdiffusion was found for the group V elements in the latter case.

Borsella *et al.*¹⁰ Reported the formation of GaN quantum dots in crystalline (quartz and sapphire) or amorphous (silica) dielectrics obtained by sequential ion implantation of Ga and N followed by annealing in NH₃ or NH₃/H₂. The wurtzite phase GaN dots have average dimensions of ~ 5 nm and their optical properties exhibit quantum confinement effects. XAS measurements performed at GILDA have provided important information on the local structure and its relation to the sample deposition conditions. In figure 2 we show Ga K-edge EXAFS spectra¹¹ for bulk GaN and differently prepared samples. While an overall similarity is apparent, the smaller amplitude of the second peak with respect to the first one reflects the partial incorporation of Ga atoms in the GaN clusters and indicates that a fraction of Ga atoms is also dispersed in the matrix, possibly bonded to oxygen atoms.

Finally, Spiga *et al.*^{12,13} have used XAS in conjunction with electron microscopy and Mössbauer spectroscopy to study of the formation of Sb and Sb nanoclusters in thin SiO₂ layers by low energy ion implantation. This method is among those considered to grow metallic nanoclusters in the field of microelectronics, for example for exploiting single – electron effects. It was possible to describe the development of the metal's local structure as a function of annealing; in the as-deposited samples the metal is dispersed in the oxide matrix while annealing induces the precipitation of small nanoclusters exhibiting interatomic distance contraction and structural disorder.

Figure 1
Ge K-edge EXAFS spectra Ge for quantum dots on Si(001), illustrating intermixing of Si

Figure 2
Ga K-edge EXAFS spectra for differently prepared GaN quantum dots and for bulk GaN

Dopants and ion implantation

The addition of foreign atoms in a semiconductor lattice is a well known way to alter or tune its physical properties. Foreign atoms can, for example, lead to the release of charge carriers (doping), the formation of charge carrier traps, or may act as luminescent centers. A description and a physical understanding of the local structure is a prerequisite for the full control of the incorporation mechanism of the foreign atom. This field is ideally suited to the application of XAS due to the sensitivity to relatively low dilutions and its local character.

One of open issues in amorphous semiconductor physics is the understanding of microscopic mechanisms of substitutional doping in hydrogenated amorphous silicon and germanium thin films. Hydrogenated amorphous germanium (a-Ge:H) is particularly interesting, due to its narrow gap, for the production of infrared sensitive devices. Most of the potential advantages, however, rely on the ability of controlling the electronic properties of the active semi-conducting layer by chemical doping. One of the most important aspects of this process is the chemical role of the dopant species. This is an important question since most physical properties of amorphous semiconductors can be expected to be determined by the local energy minimization involving network relaxation around individual atoms. It is thus reasonable that different impurities will exhibit different distribution of co-ordination states. A further aspect to be clarified is how the fraction of impurities, as well as the doping-induced effects, are related to the doping efficiency.

With these motivations, an investigation on the local structure of group III and group V elements in a-Ge:H has been performed using XAFS by Dalba *et al.* and Chambouleyron *et al.*^{14,15,16}. Experiments have been performed on Ga, In, Sb and Bi dopants; data with satisfactory signal – to – noise ratio has been obtained on a concentration of Ga as low as 1.5×10^{18} at cm^{-3} (3×10^{-5} at %), a remarkable result. In Figure 3 we report the dependence on the concentration of the coordination number and the variation of Debye – Waller factor with respect to the reference for Sb, In and Ga dopants.

Figure 3
Coordination number and variation of Debye – Waller factor for selected dopants in a-Ge:H.

Figure 4
As K – edge data for As implanted in Si(001) and subjected to various oxidation processes, as described in the text

At low concentrations the group III dopants adopt the four – fold coordination of the host network; at higher concentrations, the coordination decreases to less than 3, a signature of the presence of new, electrically inactive, sites. The analysis of the bond length variations has suggested that the doping mechanism can be understood on the basis of the internal stress accumulated in the a-Ge:H network with increasing dopant concentration. Finally, a completely different behavior was found for Bi; in this case the coordination number is always low and actually *increases* with concentration; this is an indication that, because of its atomic size, Bi does not “fit” in the host network and is in accordance with its very poor efficiency as a dopant. It is important to note that the present data set on a-Ge:H do not follow the trend previously found for dopants in hydrogenated amorphous Si.

The excellent chemical and physical properties of silicon dioxide is at the base of the strong development of silicon – based microelectronic technology. In fact, thermally grown SiO₂ is a very good dielectric, an efficient barrier to dopant diffusion, and it is selectively etched with respect to Si. Furthermore, the Si/SiO₂ interface presents a low concentration of interface states and a high electron mobility. Although the growth and processing of SiO₂ is well established for intrinsic and lowly doped Si, several questions concerning the oxidation of highly doped Si, or Si with high impurity concentration, are still open. It has been demonstrated that the presence of elements such as B, As, or Ge with doses higher than about 0.11% has a strong influence on the kinetic of oxidation, with major effects also on the impurity distribution in the matrix.

Terrasi *et al.* and Colonna *et al.*^{17,18,19} studied the modification of the local structure around As and Ge implanted in Si(001) upon thermal oxidation and its relation to surface roughness. As an example, we show in Figure 4 the As K – edge XAFS data for As in Si samples subjected to various oxidation treatments. After implantation at 70 keV with doses of either 3×10^{15} or 3×10^{16} ions/cm² the samples were oxidized in dry O₂ at 1100 °C or at 920 °C in wet atmosphere. The XAFS data clearly reveal differences in the local structure. In particular, upon high temperatures, dry processing (curves B and E in the figure) the local structure is very similar to that of a well ordered substitutional As in Si site (curve A). Instead, at high dose and upon low temperature, wet, processing (curves G and H) most of the As segregates to form monoclinic SiAs precipitates which are segregated at the Si/SiO₂ interface. A completely different picture is exhibited by Ge, which due to the higher solubility in Si, was always found to form SiGe alloy precipitates. In both cases surface roughness, as probed by AFM, was found to be related to the segregation of Ge and As at the interface when the oxidation rate is faster than the dopant diffusion.

Among transition-metal impurities, iron is of key importance in InP – based optoelectronic and microwave applications, thanks to its peculiar electronic and optical properties. Due to its near-midgap deep acceptor level, Fe acts very efficiently as an electron trap and is therefore routinely used in bulk and epitaxial crystal growth to produce semiinsulating (SI) layers. Ion implantation may be used to overcome the limited equilibrium solubility of Fe in InP.

Cesca *et al.*²⁰ have performed a structural investigation of the Fe:InP system. XAS data was correlated to that obtained by electron microscopy, Rutherford backscattering and proton – induced X-ray emission (PIXE); the samples investigated have an Fe dose of 2×10^{15} at/cm². PIXE shows that in as – implanted samples Fe atoms exhibits a high substitutional fraction with the InP lattice and that annealing induces the precipitation of Fe out of the lattice. XAS data was able to exclude that these precipitates are metallic Fe or Fe oxides and showed that they are rather small clusters of iron phosphides in which Fe is octahedrally coordinated. This is evident in figure 5 in which the XAFS data for an as – implanted and an annealed sample are compared: the increase in the signal amplitude is the signature of the change from the four – fold coordinated substitutional site to a six – fold octahedral one.

Figure 5

XAFS signal at the Fe K edge for Fe implanted in InP. The increase of the signal amplitude is the signature of the formation of octahedrally coordinated iron phosphides.

Local strain and ordering in alloy epilayers

There is a considerable interest in understanding the microscopic mechanisms of lattice misfit accommodation in epitaxial layers of semiconductor pseudobinary alloys. An understanding of the structural changes accompanying heteroepitaxial growth is necessary to model a large number of effects that strain can induce, such as band alignment in heterojunctions, structural ordering processes or structural instability governing the nucleation of defects. Basic to this problem is the local description of the degrees of freedom of the atoms inside the unit cell that must be related to the long-range description typical of the macroscopic theory of elasticity. We recall that for unstrained bulk alloys XAFS has demonstrated conclusively that the variations of the lattice parameter are accommodated at a local scale mainly by bond bending, the individual bond lengths exhibiting only a weak compositional dependence.

In a number of papers on various systems this issue has been addressed by XAFS on the GILDA beamline^{21,22,23,24,25,26}. The most complete data set is that reported by Romanato *et al.*²² who have studied InGaAs alloys pseudomorphically deposited on InP(001). In figure 6 the In – As and Ga – As bond lengths are reported for the samples and for relaxed alloys, as a function of the In atomic fraction. Also shown are the behavior of the bond lengths in the bulk alloys as determined by Mikkelsen and Boyce (MB) and the predictions of the Virtual Crystal Approximation (VCA). It is quite clear that in the strained alloys the bond lengths actually *decrease* with increasing In concentration, the opposite of what happens in the bulk; this effect can be quantitatively understood as the effect at the local scale of the long range strain (compressive for [In] > 0.53, tensile for [In] < 0.53). The data also show that small uncertainties in the determination of bond lengths ($\sigma_R = 0.005$ Å) can be obtained at GILDA. In figure 6 we also show the result of the application of the macroscopic elasticity tensor to the local scale, illustrating the good agreement with the experimental data. The curve labelled by $\xi = 0$ is obtained by neglecting differences between the force constants of the In – As and Ga – As bonds (an average value is used), while that labelled by $\xi = 1$ corresponds to using individual force constants; the two limits are indistinguishable within the experimental resolution.

The finding of direct proportionality between strain and bond length variation has been extended also to the case partially relaxed epilayers by Tormen *et al.*²⁴; the same authors have also quantified the changes in the second and third shell interatomic distances by using polarization –

dependent measurements²⁵. Finally, we mention that rather subtle changes in local structure induced by the incorporation of small amounts of C in the SiGe alloy have been detected by De Salvador et al.²⁶; the measured decrease in interatomic distances and increase of static disorder with C concentration compare favorably with the result of molecular dynamics simulations.

The addition to III-V semiconductor alloys of small quantities of an isoelectronic impurity characterized by very different electronegativity and size with respect to the host lattice elements causes dramatic and unexpected changes in physical properties. For example, the incorporation of a low concentration of nitrogen (~0.1-1%) into GaAs, InGaAs, or GaP (the so-called “dilute nitrides”) leads to an anomalous giant decrease in the host band gap. In the quaternary alloy (InGa)(AsN) the relative disposition of cations and anions on their sublattices is not uniquely determined by the atomic concentration. In fact, in the zincblende structure each site of the anion (cation) sublattice can be occupied by In or Ga (As or N) without any limitation. Therefore the question of the degree of atomic ordering, i.e. the relative number of each atomic bond as a function of composition, naturally arises. Specific examples of types of atomic ordering are the random case (relative number of each type of bond equal to the concentration) or short range ordering (SRO); in the relevant case of low N concentration SRO is exhibited, in the extreme cases, by a sample having only N – In or only N – Ga bonds. For (InGa)(AsN) it has been predicted [K. Kim and A. Zunger, Phys. Rev. Lett. **86**, 2609 (2001)] that precisely this type of SRO exists, with a strong preference for In – N bonds over Ga – N ones. Moreover, SRO has been predicted to cause a significant blue shift of the band gap and hence represent an intrinsic materials limitation.

Recent measurements by Ciatto *et al.*²⁷ have shown that SRO does exist, but is significantly less pronounced than predicted. The authors have compared the In – N coordination number as measured by In – edge XAFS with the N concentration measured by Nuclear Reaction Analysis. The results are reported in figure 7. As – deposited samples (open circles) exhibit a random atomic arrangement, while annealed samples show a statistically significant deviation towards SRO. The degree of SRO falls short of the maximum possible and of that predicted (diamond in the figure).

Figure 6

In – As and Ga – As bond lengths for InGaAs/InP(001) strained epilayers and for relaxed alloys as a function of the In atomic fraction

Figure 7

The In – N coordination number versus the N concentration in (InGa)(AsN) epilayers [4.7]. Open circles are for as – deposited samples while filled circles are for annealed one.

Growth, thin films and interfaces

The applicability of XAS to study the structure of thin films and interfaces is well known. The reasons are the sensitivity to low equivalent thicknesses when fluorescence or electron yield is used, possibly in conjunction with grazing incidence, and the possibility of obtaining directional information by exploiting the polarization of the photon beam in conjunction with the orientational dependence of the dipole matrix element. It is therefore no surprise that a number of studies of the growth of ultra – thin films and of interfaces has been performed on GILDA.

GaN and related III – N compounds possess unique properties which make them extremely attractive for optoelectronic and high temperature, high power applications. They are the subject of much current interest, for example for the realization of blue – violet diode lasers. The peculiarity of nitrides is the lack of low mismatch substrates for growth; commonly used substrates are SiC and Al₂O₃. The growth on a mismatched substrates implies the possible presence of strain in the nitride epilayer, which in turn, due to the wurtzite structure, can lead to a piezoelectric contribution to polarization. Boscherini *et al.*²⁸ studied the growth of GaN on SiC(0001) using polarization dependent XAFS at the Ga K – edge. In figure 7 we show the Fourier transforms of the data, taken with the electric vector either perpendicular or parallel to the surface, for a range of thicknesses chosen to cover the range expected for strain release. The spectra exhibit an overall similarity, except for a gradual decrease in the intensity of the second peak which is related to second shell Ga – Ga scattering. A detailed analysis showed that the local structure of the epilayer is always relaxed (i.e. non – pseudomorphic). Moreover, intermixing in the Ga/Si sublattice could be ruled out. The same group more recently reported on the growth of GaN epilayers on AlN(0001)²⁹. Also in this case it was found that intermixing was absent or at most occurring over one monolayer; contrary to the case of GaN/SiC a non – negligible degree of strain was found, the magnitude of which increased for epilayers deposited at lower temperature (620 °C) and which exhibited smoother growth.

Intermixing at the interface was the issue addressed by d’Acapito *et al.*³⁰ in their investigation of GeSi superlattices. In the growth of such superlattices one of the most critical problems is difficulty in obtaining sharp interfaces between the two semiconductors. It has been recently suggested that atomic intermixing may be an intrinsic phenomenon since it reduces the strain energy due to lattice mismatch. The deposition of an Sb monolayer “surfactant” film on the Si(001)2 × 1 reconstructed substrate was recently found to reduce atomic intermixing. Using XAFS at the Ge K – edge in grazing incidence the authors probed intermixing by measuring the relative number of Ge and Si neighbors to Ge. They found that the degree of intermixing depended critically on the growth conditions and superlattice thickness.

Figure 7

Ga K-edge XAFS data for GaN epilayers on SiC(0001) recorded with the electric vector either parallel or perpendicular to the interface; thick continuous line: 15 nm; thin continuous line: 1.5 nm; dotted line: 0.7 nm.

Metal Cluster

The interest of the research on metal nanoclusters is due to their peculiar physical-chemical properties related to the finite size effect that interesting from both a fundamental and a technological point of view. The research on metal nanoclusters performed at the GILDA beamline covers a wide range of different nanostructured materials that have a specific technological interest in the field of catalysis (Pt, Rh, Pd-based nanoclusters), optoelectronics/microelectronics and magnetic recording (for nanoclusters made of ferromagnetic elements). The investigation was focused on the aggregation processes for the formation of mono- and multi-elemental nanoclusters embedded in a matrix or supported on an amorphous or crystalline substrate; much effort was also deserved to investigate the stability of the nanostructures upon post-preparation treatments (irradiation with laser or light ions, heating in selected atmosphere). In these systems the concentration of the metal that can aggregate in nanoclusters is usually low: the intense photon flux (10^9 - 10^{11} ph/s) in a widely extended energy range (4 to 90 keV) coupled to an efficient detection system (13 elements HP-Ge detector) available at the GILDA beamline are mandatory to perform x-ray absorption and diffraction experiments. The results obtained have contributed to explain some of the processes that lead to the formation of different kind of nanostructures and indicate specific routes to improve the control on the cluster composition.

Monoelemental clusters

Consider first the nanophase systems whose nanostructure features are not due to an interaction with a supporting medium. EXAFS was used to investigate nanophase palladium: the interest in this research originates from the high density of grain boundaries, that can alter important physical properties of the material. The novel result obtained by the EXAFS experiment at the GILDA beamline is that the reduction in average coordination number can be explained by a size-effect due to the non-negligible interface-to-bulk ratio of the material^{31,32,33}.

The understanding of the cluster-matrix interaction is fundamental for many applications. When the nanoclusters interact with a supporting medium, their structure is determined not only by the finite-size effects but also the cluster-matrix interaction. About systems formed by metal nanoclusters embedded in a matrix, those that involve dielectric matrices exhibit peculiar properties: due to dielectric and quantum-confinement effects, metal nanoclusters doped glasses show an enhanced optical Kerr susceptibility, whose real part is related to the intensity-dependent refractive index, with potential application in optical switching technology. The research performed at the GILDA beamline on this subject was focused on nanometer-sized metal clusters synthesized within silicate glasses by various techniques involving the use of ion-beams. In particular, the ion implantation of the metal species in silica matrix can promote the dopant aggregation in metallic clusters: the use of the EXAFS spectroscopy has shown that the fraction of the dopant that clusterize depends not only on the implantation condition and on the local atomic density, but also on the chemical reactivity of the dopant with the matrix and on its diffusion coefficient; the interatomic distance of the atoms that aggregate in small nanoclusters can be shorter than the corresponding bulk value; the part of atoms that do not clusterize remain dispersed in the matrix and oxidized^{34,35,36,37}. Post implantation thermal treatments such as annealing in inert or reducing atmospheres can be used to increase the fraction of dopant that aggregates and also to promote the cluster growth. Similar systems are produced by ion-exchange process of silicate glasses followed by suitable post-exchange treatments. In particular, it has been demonstrated that the size of the Ag nanoclusters can be tailored by either annealing and by irradiation with laser or light ions^{38,39,40,41}.

Finally, exploiting the ion implantation of Co in Ag films (Co concentration=0.10-0.70 at%), it has been evidenced the formation of Co dimers, that are somewhat contracted with respect to the bulk

Co nearest neighbor distance and distributed in a chainlike configuration with each dimer at 90 deg from each other along opposite square faces of the Ag fcc lattice⁴².

Figure 8

Fourier transform of the EXAFS spectra (Co K-edge) from Co-implanted Ag at different Co concentration; the spectra are compared with those of Co foil and of a Co₈ clusters.

Multielemental nanoclusters

In the last few years, the possibility of realization of metal alloy nanoclusters has been exploited. With respect to the monoelemental case, one has an additional parameter to play with for controlling nanoclusters properties, i.e., the composition. Before the “tunability” of the nanoclusters properties can be used for actual devices, a careful control over alloy clusters synthesis and stability has to be achieved, in order to clarify which are the parameters (i.e., implantation conditions, subsequent thermal or laser annealings, ion irradiation, etc.) that can promote separation (via oxidation, for instance) instead of alloying of the implanted species. On the other hand, this field opens new tasks in the comprehension of the physical and chemical processes on which the alloy synthesis is based.

Part of the research performed at the GILDA beamline was about bimetallic catalysts, both RhPt and Pd-Ag metal clusters: these last are used in hydrogenation reactions, where molecules can undergo several different reactions, because they can eliminate undesired reactions and maximize the desired ones. The EXAFS spectroscopy, applied to these systems, evidenced how the formation of single metal clusters or alloy takes place, depending on the synthetic strategies used: the results indicate suitable routes to prepare systems with specific nanostructures^{43,44,45,46}.

A considerable part of the research in this field was carried out on bimetallic nanoclusters produced in silica matrix mainly by sequential ion implantation of the two ionic components. The results of the EXAFS experiments performed in these years at the GILDA beamline are mainly collected in the references^{47,48,49}; they indicate that sequential ion implantation of the two elements that should constitute the alloy is generally suitable for the synthesis of binary alloy nanoclusters⁵⁰. The alloy composition depends on the implantation fluences and on the affinity of the implanted elements with the oxygen atoms present in the matrix; the nanoclusters formed upon ion implantation are crystalline when formed of metallic elements (Cu, Ag, Au, Co, Pd, Ni, In and binary combination), and amorphous otherwise: this behavior is strictly related to the metallic chemical bonds formed by the atoms that constitute the clusters. The information obtained by the EXAFS spectroscopy have been related with the corresponding optical properties^{51,52,53}. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that suitable thermal treatments can change the alloy composition⁵⁴, in some cases leading to a chemical ordered alloy, in others leading to a de-alloying process⁵⁵: the evolution of a de-alloying upon heating in oxidizing atmosphere is not only dependent on the chemical reactivity of the metals with the O atoms, but also on the crystalline structure of the alloy clusters with respect to those one of the corresponding metal-oxides. Moreover, a deviation from the virtual crystal approximation

was evidenced by EXAFS spectroscopy in the case of Au-Cu solid solution alloy clusters, for which it is expected in the bulk phase⁵⁶.

Figure 9

Comparison of the Fourier transform moduli of the EXAFS spectra at Cu and Pd K-edges for the Pd-Cu-implanted silica, before (white markers) and after (black markers) annealing in reducing atmosphere. The effect of annealing is to increase the intermetallic signal (due to the growth of the alloy nanoclusters) and to damp the Cu-O one (due to the chemical reduction of the Cu dispersed in the matrix).

The formation of alloys that are not thermodynamically stable in the bulk (i.e. Cu-Co, Cu-Ag) has also been addressed, finding that in some specific cases the finite cluster size and the cluster-matrix interaction can actually allow it^{57,58}.

Future perspectives

Today the research on metal nanoclusters is active with different proposals accepted for the next months. It is worth to mention one accepted EXAFS experiment on carbon-metal nanoclusters obtained by supersonic cluster beam deposition: to avoid the interaction with O, it will be performed using the ultra-high vacuum chamber available at the GILDA beamline for EXAFS experiments in controlled UHV condition.

Moreover a deposition system to growth cluster is now under development at the Frascati National Laboratory. The system will be also used for in situ studies.

Among the projects in progress and the results recently achieved, two are specifically interesting for in-situ experiments on nanostructured materials. First, to perform EXAFS experiment in controlled atmosphere (in a temperature range from 77 K to 973 K), a specific cell has been designed and realized. Second, it is now operational the setup suitable to perform grazing incidence x-ray diffraction experiments with the possibility of heating the sample in-situ (up to 1200C): the first experiment has investigated the hcp->fcc martensitic transformation of Co nanoclusters embedded in silica, evidencing that the transition temperature for the nanoclusters is much higher than the corresponding value for the bulk phase (figure 10).

Figure 10

Grazing incidence x-ray diffraction pattern ($E=18$ keV) from Co nanoclusters at two different temperatures; the corresponding diffraction lines from bulk fcc and hcp Co crystals are reported for comparison. The hcp→fcc transition, pretty visible, occurs at a temperature that is about 400C above the value for the corresponding bulk phase.

Magnetic Materials

The negative magnetoresistance (MR) effect is the enhancement of electrical conductivity observed in some materials in presence of an external magnetic field. MR phenomena are relevant from an applicative point of view in the sensor field and mass storage devices. In the recent years the discover of giant (GMR) and colossal (CMR) magnetoresistance effects in some materials heavily stimulated the research interest in this field. The huge magnetoresistive effect in CMR and GMR materials originates from peculiar interplay among magnetic, electronic and structural degree of freedom making these material fascinating from a fundamental point of view and stimulating the researchers in the field of strongly correlated systems. Studies performed at GILDA mainly concern two classes of materials: the hole doped manganese oxide perovskites and the granular alloys.

Manganese oxides

Manganese oxide with perovskite structure and general formula $ReMnO_3$ ($Re=La, Pr, Ba$) may develop colossal magnetoresistance when doped with divalent metals like Ca, Sr, Pb or with Re vacancies. In these compounds the high magnetoresistance (MR) effect is closely related to temperature-induced metal to insulator (MI) transition. The theories proposed to explain the huge MR and MI transition in these compounds rely on a delicate balance between double-exchange (DE) interaction, promoting the charge mobility, and an electron-phonon (EP) coupling which depress the charge mobility. The external magnetic field enhances the DE over EP so raising the electrical conductivity.

The local structure around Mn in $La_{1-x}Ca_xMnO_3$ compounds was studied in details by EXAFS as a function of composition and temperature^{59,60} and of the applied magnetic field^{61,62}. These studies revealed in details the structural changes related to the metal to insulator transition and the influence of magnetic field on the atomic structure. In particular a clear reduction of local distortions around Mn ion has been originally put in evidence by experiments as a function of magnetic field, this effect being the micro-structural counterpart of the colossal magnetoresistance effect.

One other way to enhance magnetoresistance in Mn oxides perovskites is the vacancy doping as for $La_{1-x}MnO_{3+d}$. These compounds are easily and rapidly produced in large quantity in form of micro/nano-crystalline powders. These powders present peculiar evolution of magneto-transport

properties as a function of overall composition. An in-deep study⁶³ exploiting complementary XRD and XAS investigations revealed a phase separation effect at nanometric scale leading to the formation of a Mn perovskite phase ($\text{La}_{1-x}\text{MnO}_3$) and parasitic Mn/La oxides. The $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{MnO}_3$ phases is the only one responsible of magnetoresistance and shows a lower limit for the ratio $\text{La}/\text{Mn} > 0.9$. This limit derives from the solubility limit of La vacancies that is around 10%.

Granular alloys

Granular alloys (M_xN_{1-x}) are inhomogeneous solid mixtures of small ($\sim 1-3$ nm) magnetic (M) clusters (Fe, Co, etc...) embedded in non-magnetic matrixes (N) that can be metallic (as Cu, Ag) or insulating (as Si, SiO_2). They are super-paramagnetic materials presenting high magnetoresistance in low fields due to spin dependent scattering at the interfaces between clusters and matrix. Their properties depend on size, distribution and interactions among the particles. These compounds are prepared as metastable alloys by fast quenching, laser ablation, sputtering etc... The MR properties are optimised by opportune thermal treatments, which provoke the segregation of magnetic particles in form of nanometric clusters. The $\text{Co}_x\text{Cu}_{1-x}$ compounds have been studied in details in an exhaustive research work performed combining EXAFS, high-resolution x-ray diffraction and time resolved x-ray diffraction^{64,65,66,67,68,69,70} experiments. These studies, coupled with detailed magnetic characterization, revealed an anomaly in the thermal induced segregation process. This anomaly, related to the peculiar properties of CoCu binary phase diagram, is the principal responsible of the very reproducible behavior of the MR versus the annealing temperature, despite the alloy composition and/or the preparation method.

Surface and Interfaces

In recent years, the physical properties of two dimensional metal-oxide epilayers on metal substrates have become a topic of great interest. Films a few monolayers (ML) thick can be deposited epitaxially on metal substrates by ultrahigh vacuum techniques, yielding reproducible and well-characterized systems. It has been shown that the energy gap of the oxide, in the oxide/metal system, can be modulated by the film thickness T . The demonstrated ability to control T represents therefore a new technological opportunity for band-gap engineering. It has also been argued that the presence of the metal substrate can alter significantly the electronic structure of the oxide and influence its chemical properties, with a prospective range of important applications. In the latter respect, *ab initio* simulations of perfect oxide/metal epilayers have given so far a different indication; namely, the electronic structure of the oxide is modified only in a strict vicinity of the interface. The question has therefore been raised whether residual film defectivity could be responsible for the observed enhancement of chemical activity and other evidence of modified electronic structure; in this case a perfectly epitaxial overlayer would be a poor model of the real systems. In order to provide an accurate estimate of the geometry of the NiO/Ag(001) interface an accurate polarization – dependent XAFS investigation was performed⁷¹ and the results compared with that of electron diffraction techniques and *ab – initio* simulations. In figure 11 we show the Ni K – edge XAFS data for 3 ML NiO/Ag(001), taken with the electric vector perpendicular and parallel to the interface. The analysis of the data shows the absence of significant interdiffusion, that the 3 ML epilayer is pseudomorphically distorted with the in – plane lattice parameter equal to that of the substrate; an interface Ni – Ag signal was detected which is compatible with the growth of the epilayer with O on top of Ag and an interface distance which is expanded compared to both the Ag and NiO lattice parameters.

Figure 11

Ni K – edge XAFS data and corresponding fits for 3 ML NiO/Ag(001). Top and bottom curves: electric vector parallel and perpendicular to the interface, respectively. The shaded area has been excluded by the fits.

Depending on the growth parameters and on the interaction with the substrate, often the growth of metal on surfaces can result in the formation of nanoclusters. In these cases the structure of the nanoclusters is determined by both finite-size effects (i.e. the presence of a surface energy leads to peculiar structures different from those of the corresponding bulk phase) and by the cluster-substrate interaction.

The structural investigation of the growth of metal nanoclusters onto a crystalline substrate (MgO) has contributed to understand the relative magnitude of these two effects. The GILDA instrumentation allowed to record EXAFS spectra from deposited metal films whose thickness can go down to 0.5 monolayer (ML). By exploiting the polarized nature of the synchrotron radiation it was also possible to measure the interatomic correlations in the direction parallel to the substrate surface. In particular, it has been assessed that while Cu atoms deposited onto MgO (001) aggregates in nanoclusters whose interaction with the substrate is weak⁷², for Ag atoms deposited on a MgO(100) surface⁷³, the clusters behave in a way similar to free clusters for film thickness lower than 1 ML, while for thickness between 1 and 3 ML the interaction with the crystalline matrix affects the interatomic distances.

RE is found to be bound to F atoms and no RE-RE coordinations show up at the highest concentration values. Moreover, the study showed that independently from the precursor used in the glass melt (Pr chloride, oxide or sulfide) the structure of the Pr first shell in the final glass is always the same and is very similar to the complex structure observed in PrF_3 . These findings were also confirmed by Anomalous X-Ray Scattering data also collected at GILDA⁷⁶, on the same samples.

The group of the Trento University has carried out a number of studies devoted to the determination of the RE environment in sol-gel materials⁷⁷ with particular attention to the process of gel densification in the case of matrices doped with Pr⁷⁸, Tb⁷⁹ and Er⁸⁰ ions. In order to correctly account for the asymmetric Radial Distribution Function (RDF) of the first neighbours observed in these systems, a peculiar data analysis method, based on the determination from the EXAFS data of the shape of the RDF. In all cases (i.e. Pr, Tb and Er doped gels) the RE is bound to O atoms of the matrix; the gel densification process leads to a reduction of the number of O first neighbours, a shortening of the first-shell bond-length and an asymmetric form of the first peak of the RDF towards high R values. The latter effect is particularly marked in the Pr case (figure 13) whereas a much less pronounced asymmetric form of the RDF is observed for Er doped samples. An intermediate behavior between Er and Pr was observed in the Tb case. No RE-RE coordination was evidenced at the highest concentrations and, in the case of Al-codoped matrices, a preferential coupling of Er to Al second neighbors was found. The absence of visible RE-RE coordination, observed also in other systems studied on GILDA, is of paramount importance in the interpretation of the phenomenon of luminescence lifetime shortening upon increase of the concentration (luminescence quenching phenomenon) that was previously attributed to the formation of direct RE-RE bonds in the matrix.

Figure 13
Example of the asymmetric shape of the RDF of O ions around Pr^{3+} ions in sol-gel samples

A detailed description of the Er and Yb sites in silicate^{81,82} and phosphate⁸³ glasses has been given by using the Multiple Scattering (MS) formalism to interpret the EXAFS signal. In this way, a link of RE to the non-bonding oxygens in the polyhedra (SiO_4 or PO_4) constituting the glassy matrix has been evidenced, as well as a well defined RE-O-Si(or P) bonding angle, around 135 deg. No evolution of the site with the RE concentration from below to above the luminescence concentration quenching value has been observed and in particular no evidence of RE-RE coordination has been found in all cases studied. On the other hand, by studying Silica-titania-alumina glasses a preferential coordination of Er with Al in second shell was found in agreement with other studies on similar systems. In order to obtain a more stringent determination of the RE local site an experiment at the RE K edges ($\text{Er}_K = 57486$ eV, $\text{Yb}_K = 61332$ eV) has been carried out.

In this way, by avoiding the interference of neighboring L edges, we had access to high values of the photoelectron wavevector k necessary to well evidence the RE-RE coordination. The experiments were carried out in dynamical focusing mode and using an original method based on the 3rd harmonic emission from a 311 Si monochromating crystal⁸⁴ and permitted to rule out the occurrence of RE-RE coordination and provided the basis of an original model for RE clustering in glasses (figure 14) that accounts for the approaching of the RE ions and the absence of RE-RE coordination observed in EXAFS data.

Figure 14

Data at the Er K edge on Er doped sol-gel glasses. The inset shows the clustering model proposed.

Er doped Silicon

Erbium has revealed to be of extreme interest for its luminescent properties also in Silicon technology. It has been demonstrated the feasibility of obtaining electro-luminescence in Er doped Si devices by doping Si wafers with Er⁸⁵. Due to the fact that the equilibrium concentration of substitutional Er in Si is well below the minimum needed for device applications and that the formation of Er silicide leads to poorly luminescent sites, the co-doping with O ions revealed to be necessary in order to obtain good optical properties. An EXAFS study⁸⁶ evidenced the dynamics of the process: it was shown that in as-implanted Er + O specimens, Er forms the silicide phase. The formation of Er-O bonds is obtained only after suitable thermal annealing that promotes the crystallization of the matrix and the migration of O ions, triggering the reaction with Er (figure 15).

Figure 15
Evolution of the Er environment upon annealing in Er + O implanted Si

A similar behaviour was observed also for Er + F doped samples⁸⁷. A detailed analysis of these data in the MS formalism has permitted to describe in detail the site of Er + O clusters in Si [DAC-04] that exhibits a well defined Er-O bond length as well as a well defined Er-O-Si bond angle similarly to what observed in glasses. These experimental data rule out the occurrence of Er in tetrahedral interstitial T_i or substitutional T_s sites described in a number of with previous theoretical calculations and are compatible with the positioning of Er ions in O-decorated the hexagonal interstitial H_i sites.

Pizzini⁸⁸ reported a refined analysis of the EXAFS spectrum of a series of samples, some obtained by liquid phase epitaxy (LPE) growth and others by ion (co-)implantation. The spectra were analyzed up to 4 Å interatomic distances using *ab-initio* simulations and the GNXAS software, thus providing a detailed local structural analysis. In samples which did not exhibit luminescence the $ErSi_2$ structure was found, while differences between optically active samples were detected, co-implanted samples having a more disordered oxide environment than those grown by LPE.

Also the site of Er in other crystals likes $BaTiO_3$ ⁸⁹ or $LiNbO_3$ ⁹⁰ have been studied, providing a complete description of the site of the RE.

Ion exchanged materials

Ion exchange is a process of particular interest in the fabrication of buried waveguides. Doping ions like Ag^+ , K^+ or Cu^+ are introduced in the glassy matrix by diffusion and they exchange place with the other ions constituting the host glass. An example is the $Ag \leftrightarrow Na$ exchange in the soda-lime glass. Studies have been carried out with the aim of determining the local order around different exchanged ions. In the case of Ag exchanged glasses⁹¹ the Ag ions are bound to O in the matrix with a bond length ($R_{Ag-O}=2.19$ Å) significantly longer than that found in the silver oxide $R_{Ag-O}=2.04$ Å, evidencing a looser bond with the matrix. On the other hand, in the case of Cu exchanged soda-lime glasses⁹² it was evidenced that Cu is in the Cu^+ ionic state and the bond length with the O ions in the matrix are $R_{Cu-O}=1.86$ Å, coincident with the value for Cu_2O crystalline oxide. This evidences that, for Cu, the bond with the matrix is noticeably stronger than in the case of Ag, and this is in agreement with the lower diffusion of Cu ions in the matrix. The depth profile of Cu^{2+} ions in the matrix was carried out by comparing data in fluorescence yield (XFY) and in total electron yield (TEY). The result was that, within the range of TEY, no presence of Cu^{2+} was detected. The analysis was recently repeated⁹³ by using glancing incidence EXAFS (figure 16): in this way the probed depth could be varied from 4nm to 5 μm and the presence of Cu^{2+} ions was in the shallower part of the exchanged layer. An original theoretical model on the diffusion of the Cu^+/Cu^{2+} pair has been derived that can explain the observed experimental data.

Figure 16

Evolution of the XANES spectrum in a Cu exchanged sodalime sample measured at different glancing angles. In the figure are indicated the estimated extinction length value corresponding to the collection angle, as well as the fits that provide the $\text{Cu}^+/\text{Cu}^{2+}$ ratio

Glass structure and ion conductivity in glasses

Ionic conduction in glasses has turned out to be difficult to understand, at least at the microscopic level. The main reason for these troubles arises from the structural complexity of glasses. Associated with the ion conduction and ion transport in glasses is the so called mixed mobile ion (MMI) effect which manifests itself as a strong decrease in ionic dc conductivity in glasses where two mobile alkali-metal ions are mixed, as compared to the single alkali-metal glasses. The models proposed to motivate the conductivity drop either assuming major structural changes under addition of a second ion, or introducing an interaction between dissimilar ions, so as to create immobile ion pairs. A comprehensive study⁹⁴ on $\text{Li}_x\text{Rb}_{1-x}$, $\text{Li}_x\text{Na}_{1-x}$ and $\text{Li}_x\text{Rb}_{1-x}$ doped PO_3 glasses was done combining anomalous-XRD and neutron diffraction data. The 3D structural models derived from reverse Monte Carlo analysis allow excluding both the previous models suggesting, on the contrary, that the MMI effect is due to the large mismatch between the local potential of site A and the induced potential of ion B which results in a high activation energy for ionic jump to dissimilar sites so decreasing the conductivity.

In a following work⁹⁵ the local structure of AgPO_3 doped glasses ($\text{Y}_x(\text{AgPO}_3)_{1-x}$ with $\text{Y} = \text{CsI}, \text{AgI}, \text{PbI}$) was studied combining x-ray and neutron diffraction data. The AgPO_3 doped glasses depict anomalous ion conductivity as a function of composition: the conductivity is higher doping with PbI , intermediate with AgI , while it is suppressed doping with CsI . The structural models derived from the reverse Monte Carlo (RMC) method allow the understanding of ionic conductivity as determined from the balance of three effects: two of them promote the ionic conductivity, they are the network expansion and the partial Ag dissociation. The third effect, on the contrary, reduces the conductivity and is a mixed mobile ion effect due to the presence of Cs ions in these glasses. In case of Pb the conductivity enhancement can be denoted as immobile ion effect and must be attributed to the fact that Pb has a strong tendency to coordinate oxygen thus putting the Ag in a mainly iodine environment.

Atomic structure and biophysics

The local structure of active metal site in proteins

The chemical selectivity, local order sensitivity and the possibility to probe high-diluted samples are peculiar capabilities of X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy, which have unique importance probing the atomic structure of biological materials. They offer, as example, the possibility to directly probe the protein active sites in their physiological environment, differently, for example, from single crystal diffraction techniques.

The X-ray absorption spectroscopy capabilities were originally exploited to carefully probe the interaction between Zn ions and myelin basic protein (MBP) in Langmuir-Blodgett (LB) multilayers^{96,97,98}. The multilayers were taken as a model for the multi lamellar structure of the myelin sheet, the membrane surrounding the nerve axon, which plays a crucial role for nervous signal transduction. XAS data were collected either with or without MBP in the multilayer. The the extended (EXAFS) and near edge (XANES) region of the XAS spectra at the Zn K-edge were quantitatively analysed. EXAFS results proved that the Zn ions are mainly bounded to the heads of the phospholipid molecules of the LB layers either with or without MBP. The quantitative structural refinement of the XANES region of the spectra, performed through the recently developed MXAN approach allowed to get a deeper look into the topological Zinc environment modification induced modifying the hydration and/or inserting the MBP in the multilayer. These studies unambiguously demonstrate that the Zn ions directly interact with both phospholipid heads of the layers and with the myelin basic protein.

The binuclear copper site of the met and met-azido derivatives of *Octopus vulgaris* and *Carcinus aestuarii* hemocyanins at pH 7.5 were detailed by XAS⁹⁹. The analysis of EXAFS and XANES regions of the XAS spectra demonstrate that the structure of the meet-derivatives Cu site is made of five-coordinated O-bridged binuclear copper(II) centre favouring a Cu-Cu distance of 3Å

Crystallographic structure of biomaterials

The ossification processes in human foetal bone have been studied in details^{100,101,102} coupling 3D micro-imaging techniques (x-ray computed microtomography performed on ID-19), x-ray powder diffraction (performed on GILDA) and x-ray micro-diffraction (performed on ID13). Bone samples were collected from vertebral ossification centres of human foeti with gestation ages ranging in between 16 and 26 weeks. 3D images show the ossification centres as a globally isotropic structure composed of a central region (trabecular bone) and a peripheral region (immature bone). The high-resolution images (0.5 µm) gave accurate description of the architectural parameters quantifying their evolution as a function of foetal age. The x-ray powder diffraction experiments characterized the crystallographic phase of bone as a function of bone ageing. It showed that bone mineral has a hydroxyapatite-like phase (bioapatite) which appear compressed along the c-axis with respect to synthetic hydroxyapatite (Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(HO)₂). The study shows that the c-axis compression strain decreases while the bone crystallites growth as a function of foetal age. This effect could be related to compositional changes. Microdiffraction investigation (~5µm beam size) directly probed the crystallographic structure in a single trabecula highlighting the crystallographic differences along the volume. In particular the compressive strain along the c-axis is higher at the trabecula surface (where the mineral bone is less mature) and decreases in the bulk where mature mineral bone is present.

Earth Sciences

The beamline activity in the Earth Sciences in the period 1996-2003 represents about 12 % of the total activity in terms of the number of experiments (39 approved experiments on a total of 317). In

line with the due proportion of public beamtime, about 1/3 of the experiments were allocated by the ESRF Beamtime Allocation Panels (CH, HC, ME), and 2/3 of the experiments were allocated through the Italian Beamtime Review Panel. Both Italian and public experiments related to the Earth Sciences are equally distributed between the two available techniques: 19 experiments required XAS and 20 experiments required XRD.

In general the research projects that have been allocated beam time consistently produced significant results at the international level, as shown by the quality and number of publications. The publication record lists about 25 publications on peer reviewed international journals, which makes an average of more than 1 publication every 2 experiments. The number of abstracts, reports, and communications to conferences is about twice the number of publications.

Concerning the scientific activities in the field of Earth Sciences, they can be grouped into four broad research areas:

1. geo-chemistry of minor and trace elements in geological glasses
2. local crystal chemistry of major and minor elements in rock-forming silicates and solid solutions
3. crystallography and crystal structure of mineral phases and synthetic analogues
4. time-resolved XRD experiments of dynamic processes

Geo-Chemistry

The research on geological glasses has been performed by XAS in order to assess the valence state and the local structure of specific cations in natural glasses of different origin. Two problems are addressed: (a) the crystal chemistry and structural role of Fe in glasses related to meteoric impacts, especially tektites^{103,104} and (b) the role of elemental tracers in silicate glasses of magmatic origin. Both research activities have significant implications for the modeling of the physical properties of silicate liquids and the history of earth and planetary materials.

Silicate solid solutions

The research on silicate solid solutions attempts to use XAS spectroscopy as a complement to the diffraction-based structural methods to understand the local coordination and arrangement of specific elements in the crystal structure. The project concerns specifically garnet solid solutions in the almandine-spessartine and pyrope-grossular joins, which are important constituents of metamorphic and mantle rocks. The aim is to understand the non-ideal properties of garnet solid solutions, and identify the crystal chemical role of trace components, mainly REE elements, in the garnet structure^{105,106,107,108}.

Crystal structure investigations

Although the beamline is not optimized for high angular resolution and structure analysis, the structural aspect of mineralogical crystallography is represented by a variety of experiments, mainly performed by powder diffraction using the full-profile approach, and sometimes complemented and supported by absorption spectroscopic data. Interesting structural studies have been performed on rock minerals and synthetic analogues of industrial importance^{109,110,111,112,113}. The combined DAFS approach has been attempted with limited success on spinel-type compounds. Interesting results have been obtained on amorphous precursor of industrial ceramics using differential WAXS techniques¹¹⁴. A number of experiments aimed to characterize the crystal chemical role of structural and sorbed species on layer silicates, some of these studies have potential environmental interest^{115,116}.

Time resolved diffraction

The time-resolved diffraction experiments certainly were a major focus of the Earth Sciences experiments at the beamline. This is fully understandable as the beamline instrumental setup,

encompassing the translating image plate¹¹⁷, is optimized for high throughput medium-resolution dynamic XRD experiments. Accordingly, two thirds of the diffraction experiments were performed on dynamic processes such as phase transitions, chemical reactions, thermal treatments of industrial minerals, and so on. This activity of the beamline in this field is highly successful and the impressive publication record demonstrates the quality and the impact of the results^{118,119,120,121,122,123,124,125,126,127}.

Archaeological and Cultural Heritage Science at GILDA

The use of materials science techniques has long been exploited to address questions posed by archaeologists, particularly those of provenance of ancient materials and technological aspects of production. Identification of the chemical content of ancient objects and of their structures is an important step in these studies and any non-destructive technique that can give this type of information is of particular relevance.

Synchrotron radiation based X-ray techniques, which have enabled the technological advancement of many fields in materials science, have been recently applied to archaeology and cultural heritage problems.

In particular, it has been shown that XAS spectroscopy is a very useful technique to be applied in archaeological studies. In fact, it is a non-destructive method which can be applied in air; it virtually does not require any restriction on the type and size of the sample, which can be metal, ceramic, glass, cloth, wood, etc. and, finally, it is applicable to most of the elements of interest, even in very low concentrations. All these characteristics are particularly important in archaeological applications, in which samples are precious cultural heritage made of many different materials.

Specifically, at GILDA beamline, XAS technique has been successfully applied to the study of the the origin of color and ancient production technology of Roman and Medieval glass and to the study of of luster decorations in glazes of Renaissance pottery. This study was described in the Science Update section of Nature published on June the 30th 2003.

Origin of colour and ancient production technology of Roman and Medieval glass age

It is well known that the color exhibited by glasses can be determined by the oxidation state and the electronic configuration of the metal ions in them. These are usually elements belonging to the transition row of the periodic table, which absorb characteristic frequencies of the visible region as a result of d-d electronic transitions. In particular, ancient glasses often contain iron at levels which can impart a typical incidental green coloration. To minimize this problem, from around the middle of the first millennium BC, substances were added which tended to neutralize the colorant effects of the iron. Before the Roman period antimony was the main decolorant, while from the second century BC manganese become. Since the characterization of colorant and decolorant components is important in understanding the manufacturing technique of the ancient glasses, X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy with synchrotron radiation has been applied to the study of the oxidation state of iron and manganese in a number of glass samples of archaeological interest, characterized by different colors (from green to pale brown to uncolored).

The samples are:

1. fragments of perfume bottles of the 2nd century AD, found in the Patti Roman Villa (Sicily)^{128,129,130};
2. “production indicators” of the medieval glasshouse of Val Gargassa, that is, those remains which testify specific operations carried out during the productive cycle, implying fritting, melting, flashing (mixing), boiling and working¹³¹.
3. opaque and transparent game counters of different colors found in Pompeii excavations^{132,133};

This project aimed to characterize the different aspects of the ancient glass manufacturing technique, the origin of color in findings with different chromatic tonalities, the influence of iron oxidation state on the color of the glass in the different steps of the production cycle and finally the possible decolorant role of manganese oxide in the colorless glass.

The glasses from Patti Villa are, from the chemical point of view, rather similar to each other, suggesting a similar mineralogical composition of the materials used for their production. In particular, they can be defined as ‘low-magnesia’ glasses, in agreement with their Roman origin. Moreover, all glasses contain iron and manganese, with the exception of one sample characterized by a bottle-green color, which is lacking in manganese.

The Fe and Mn K-edge XANES spectra and the detailed structure of the pre-edge peak of these

Fig. 1 – Fe K-edge XANES spectra of the three ancient glasses and the Fe-reference compounds

samples and of the reference compounds have shown that in the uncolored ancient glasses iron is mainly present as Fe^{3+} , while manganese is present in the reduced form Mn^{2+} , confirming the hypothesis of a redox interaction between iron and manganese ($\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Mn}^{4+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{Mn}^{2+}$), as a result of a deliberate addition of pyrolusite as decolorant during the melting procedure.

A similar conclusion was reached for the glass samples from the Medieval Val Gargassa glasshouse: the complete uncolored glass was obtained by adding pyrolusite (MnO_2) as specific decolorant, even if modifications of the furnace atmosphere in a specific production step (presumably during boiling) were also used to produce slightly different green-colored artifacts.

The most interesting result obtained from the XAFS study of the game counters from Pompeii excavations is the speciation of copper in one red opaque sample. The chemical analysis and the SEM studies revealed the presence of an anomalously high content of Cu, finely dispersed in the glass ground mass, but did not allow to determine its oxidation state. The analysis of the XANES spectra collected at Cu K-edge indicates the presence of both Cu^+ and Cu^0 . However, the red color is attributed to the metallic copper, since the oxidized species Cu^+ is present in other numerous glass artifacts of the same period that are characterized by different tonalities from green to blue-green.

Copper and silver in glazes of Renaissance luster pottery: nanoparticles, ions and local environment

Metal–glass nanocomposites, formed by nanometer-sized crystalline metal clusters embedded in a glass matrix, are characterized by specific optical and magnetic properties. In particular, due to the third order optical nonlinearities, they are of current interest in the development of glass-based devices for optoelectronics. It has been recently found that luster decorations, typical of the Medieval

and Renaissance pottery of the Mediterranean basin, substantially consist of a metal–glass nanocomposite thin layer. Indeed, by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) it has been shown that luster consists of a thin film composed of a heterogeneous distribution of silver and copper nanoparticles of sizes ranging from 5 to 100 nm. These decorations show peculiar optical properties, producing brilliant reflections of different colors, cangiant effects, and iridescence.

In spite of the large historical documentation, only little scientific information on luster is available. Luster chromatic effects are expected to depend on the properties of the nanoparticle colloidal dispersion. However, luster optical properties may also be influenced by the presence of ionic copper in the glaze because, when present in specific oxidation, it could modify the glaze refraction index or even contribute directly to its coloration. In addition, copper ions can play a relevant role in the luster formation mechanism. To investigate the presence of nanoparticles and of copper ions in the luster glaze and to determine copper ion states and their local order, a study has been performed on the original samples of Umbrian Renaissance luster pottery exclusively by nondestructive techniques, among which XAFS^{134,135,136}. Elemental analyses indicate that gold decorations are characterized by silver and copper, while red decorations by copper only. The chromatic effects are determined by the fraction of metal ions reduced to nanoparticles. Specifically, silver nanoparticles determine the gold color, while the red color is determined by nanoparticles of copper. EXAFS measurements, carried out at the Cu and Ag *K* edge, indicate that in both gold and red luster copper is mostly in the oxidized form (Cu^+ and Cu^{++}) with a large prevalence of Cu^+ . States and local environment of copper ions are similar to those found in copper–alkali ion-exchanged silicate glass samples. This strongly supports the view that luster formation is mediated by a copper– and silver–alkali ion exchange as a first step, followed by nucleation and growth of metal nanoparticles.

The red luster has also been studied by EXAFS measurements carried out in the total yield mode, to probe only the first 150 nm of the glaze layer. These data indicated that in some cases lustre nanoclusters may be confined in a very thin layer close to the surface.

Ag *K*-edge EXAFS data recorded on gold luster suggest the presence of both metallic and oxidized silver. The presence of silver nanoparticles is confirmed by the fact that silver coordinates about eight silver atoms at a distance of $2.88 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$.

EXAFS studies of lattice dynamics and thermal expansion

EXAFS is considered a well-established technique for the study of local *structure* in *disordered materials* (glasses, random alloys, catalysts, proteins, etc.). It is however possible to obtain from EXAFS original information also on *dynamical properties* of *crystalline* as well as non-crystalline materials, through accurate temperature dependent measurements and peculiar data analysis procedures.

The relevance of EXAFS studies as a function of temperature is twofold. On the one hand, careful measurements on simple model crystals allow a deeper understanding of the relationships between EXAFS parameters and local properties of materials; as a result, a widespread increase of accuracy in structural characterisations could be obtained. On the other hand, peculiar information can be gained on correlation of atomic motion and local thermal expansion; in addition to the interest for testing dynamical theories and models, including anharmonicity effects, these results give original insights on the local mechanisms of technologically interesting phenomena, like ionic conduction or negative thermal expansion.

In 1976, Beni and Platzman (Phys. Rev. B 14 (1976) 1514) studied thermal effects on EXAFS, within the harmonic approximation, and evidenced the correlation effects in the EXAFS Debye-Waller factor. Relatively little attention was dedicated to the subject in subsequent years, in spite of the improvements in the anharmonic analysis of weakly disordered systems allowed by the cumulant method (Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. 207 (1983) 437; for a review, see J. Synchrotron Rad. 4

(1997) 243). A significant progress was made by two pioneering papers on AgI: in the first one (Phys. Rev. B 41 (1990) 9668) the strong correlation in the EXAFS Debye-Waller factor was connected to the peculiar dynamical properties of AgI; in the second one (Phys. Rev. B 52 (1995) 149) the difference between the distances measured by EXAFS and diffraction was for the first time experimentally evidenced and attributed to the relative vibrational motion perpendicular to the bond. In a subsequent, more refined work on germanium (Phys. Rev. Lett. 89 (2002) 25503), the comparison between EXAFS and diffraction allowed a reliable quantitative determination of the intensity of the 1st-shell relative perpendicular motion, and low-temperature quantum effects on the third cumulant were for the first time detected.

These results stimulated the development of an articulated research program, aiming at studying other systems of different structure and complexity. Crystalline copper is being investigated for calibration purposes, to check the ultimate accuracy attainable by EXAFS measurements and analyses (J. Synchrotron Rad. 8 (2001) 1214.). The leading part of the research program concerns investigations on systems affected by Negative Thermal Expansion (NTE) of geometrical origin, exploiting the peculiar EXAFS sensitivity to the expansion of selected inter-atomic distances and to the vibrations perpendicular to nearest-neighbour bonds. Measurements have already been done on Cu₂O and Ag₂O, two crystals sharing the same framework structure. Further experiments are planned on other NTE materials, like CuCl and CuScO₂. Local dynamics and thermal expansion are an interesting topic of research also for super-ionic materials, in view of their relationship with the motion of mobile ions: a refinement work on AgI and systematic investigations on AgI-containing silver borate and molybdate glasses are under way or planned.

An EXAFS spectrum is the superposition of contributions from different single scattering (SS) and multiple scattering (MS) paths. Owing to thermal motion, the EXAFS signal of each scattering path samples a one-dimensional distribution of instantaneous path-lengths. For SS paths (corresponding to coordination shells), the EXAFS signal samples the distribution of instantaneous inter-atomic distances r . For moderately disordered systems, phase and amplitude of the EXAFS signal of a given coordination shell can be parametrised in terms of the first odd and even cumulants, respectively, of the distance distribution. First cumulant $C_1^* = \langle r \rangle$ and second cumulant $C_2^* = \langle (r - \langle r \rangle)^2 \rangle$ correspond to mean and variance of the distribution, respectively, while the third cumulant $C_3^* = \langle (r - \langle r \rangle)^3 \rangle$ measures its asymmetry. The typical outcome of an EXAFS experiment, aiming at dynamical studies, consists in the values of the first three or four cumulants as a function of temperature. The EXAFS cumulants can be connected to the force constants of an effective one-dimensional pair potential, through a perturbative quantum approach.

Let us now connect the one-dimensional EXAFS cumulants to the structural and dynamical properties of a three-dimensional crystal. Let R_c be the distance between the average positions of the central atom and one of its neighbours. The instantaneous relative thermal displacement of the two atoms, $\Delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_0$, can be decomposed into its projections Δu_{\parallel} and Δu_{\perp} along the bond direction and in the perpendicular plane, respectively ($\Delta u^2 = \Delta u_{\parallel}^2 + \Delta u_{\perp}^2$). To good approximation, the second cumulant measures the *parallel* MSRD (Mean Square Relative Displacement): $C_2^* = \langle \Delta u_{\parallel}^2 \rangle$, which is the sum of the two uncorrelated MSDs, obtainable from diffraction, minus the parallel Displacement Correlation Function (DCF).

One can also show that the average distance $C_1^* = \langle r \rangle$, measured by EXAFS, is larger than the distance R_c between average positions, measured by diffraction: $C_1^* \approx R_c + \langle \Delta u_{\perp}^2 \rangle / 2R_c$. Accordingly, also the thermal expansion measured by EXAFS is larger than the expansion measured by diffraction. Conversely, by comparing EXAFS and diffraction results, one can obtain the *perpendicular* MSRD $\langle \Delta u_{\perp}^2 \rangle$.

The EXAFS thermal expansion (measured by the 1st cumulant) is a joint effect of the asymmetry of the effective EXAFS pair potential (measured by the 3rd cumulant) and a shift of its minimum position. The EXAFS effective potential cannot be identified with the interaction potential between a pair of atoms, since it depends on the statistically averaged behaviour of all the atoms in the crystal, and is in principle temperature dependent. This dependence on temperature can give

information on subtle physical effects. As a matter of fact, the relative vibrations perpendicular to the bond direction induce a positive shift of the effective potential, as observed in copper and germanium. In AgI and CdSe a negative shift has been instead observed, whose origin has still to be clarified.

Dynamical studies require both very accurate experiments and suitable interpretation schemes. The analysis of the *1st coordination shell* signal can generally be done within the single scattering approximation using the ratio method to obtain accurate relative values of EXAFS cumulants. The analysis of the *outer coordination shells* is by far more complicated, owing to the difficulty of disentangling their single contributions and to the effects of multiple scattering; a purely phenomenological analysis is generally inaccurate, and one has to resort to simulation and non-linear fitting procedures. Such studies allow

A) The calibration of EXAFS

The regular temperature dependence of EXAFS cumulants, according to the quantum perturbative model, is a good self-consistency check of their reliability. The inclusion of the third cumulant in the EXAFS analysis is necessary to guarantee the accuracy of the 1st cumulant values. The quantitative evaluation of the difference between EXAFS and diffraction distances increases the soundness of the interpretation of EXAFS results; multiple scattering contributions could be more effectively calculated if the effect of perpendicular MSRDS were properly taken into account.

B) The test of dynamical theories

The reproductions of both parallel and perpendicular MSRDS represent an original and independent test of the phase relationships between eigenvectors of the dynamical matrix, obtained from ab-initio or model calculations. (A good fit to experimental dispersion curves is a test of eigen-frequencies, not of eigen-vectors). The reproduction of 3rd and higher order cumulants represents a test for dynamical calculations including the effects of anharmonicity [7].

C) The study of negative thermal expansion materials

In many systems, negative thermal expansion (NTE) is observed in temperature ranges of different extent, and can be attributed to geometrical effects of low-frequency vibrations perpendicular to some inter-atomic links: guitar string effect in simple crystals with diamond or zinc-blende structure, rigid unit modes (RUM) in framework structures, etc. These vibrations induce an overall contraction, which opposes and sometimes overcomes the positive expansion due to the potential anharmonicity. The possibility of measuring the real expansion of selected bonds and the perpendicular MSRDS, offered by EXAFS, represents an effective tool for directly monitoring the local behaviour of NTE materials, complementary to Bragg diffraction and alternative to the less accurate and less simple analysis of thermal diffuse scattering in total scattering experiments.

The Gilda beam-line is well equipped for accurate temperature dependent EXAFS measurements. Two cryostats, liquid-He and liquid-N, cover the temperature ranges 4-300 and 78-500 K, respectively. It is the only ESRF line effectively covering the 4-20 K range. An extension above 500 K is highly desirable. The extremely high accuracy level required for dynamical studies could be attained only quite recently, after some problems of monochromator mechanical stability were solved; the scientific production is thus concentrated in the last years of activity.

Studies actually performed regards copper^{137,138,139,140} and copper and silver oxide^{141,142,143}.

Copper

EXAFS measurements were performed in the temperature interval from 4 to 500 K.

The main results for the 1st-shell can be summarized as follow.

The 1st cumulant has a very regular temperature dependence, confirming the possibility of detecting distance variations of the order of 0.001 Å. The EXAFS thermal expansion is larger than the crystallographic one: the difference has been exploited to get the perpendicular MSRDS. The ratio between perpendicular and parallel MSRDS is about 2.5, say larger than the value 2 of a perfectly

isotropic system (Debye crystal). EXAFS can thus measure the anisotropy of the relative vibrational motion.

The 3rd cumulant exhibits the low-temperature quantum deviation from the classical parabolic behaviour. The thermal expansion extracted from the 3rd cumulant differs from both the 1st cumulant and the crystallographic thermal expansion. In principle, the crystallographic thermal expansion cannot be directly obtained from EXAFS. The experimental relative values of the 1st-shell cumulants are in good agreement with the values calculated by means of path-integral Monte Carlo techniques.

The analysis of the outer shells (2nd, 3rd and 4th), entangled and contaminated by MS contributions, was globally performed through theoretical simulation, including relevant MS paths. A reasonable agreement between theory and experiment could be obtained only after a drastic reduction of the fitting parameters. The relative thermal expansion of all paths could be reasonably described only by a unique expansion parameter, in satisfactory agreement with the crystallographic expansion, but unable to give information on perpendicular MSRDS of the different shells. Accurate values were instead obtained for the parallel MSRDS. Best-fits of the MSRDS of the 4 shells gave Debye temperatures in agreement with the diffraction and specific heat values. A slightly lower value was however found for the 2nd shell, corresponding to a weaker correlation along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction, in agreement with recent dynamical calculations of fcc metals.

Ag₂O and Cu₂O

The measurements at the Ag K edge in Ag₂O were done from 7 to 500 K, at average steps of 50 K, in 1999, to investigate on thermal expansion. The first results show that the 2nd-shell Ag-Ag distance decreases at increasing temperature, in qualitative agreement with the negative thermal expansion (NTE) measured by diffraction. On the contrary, the 1st-shell Ag-O distance neatly increases. The first-shell perpendicular MSRDS is much larger than the parallel MSRDS, and comparable with the 2nd-shell parallel MSRDS, confirming that the NTE is connected to vibrations perpendicular to the O-Ag-O chain, but also suggesting the inadequacy of models solely based on rigid unit modes.

A new set of measurements was done at the Ag K edge in Ag₂O from 4 to 100 K in 2003, at much closely spaced temperature steps, to investigate on a phase transition observed below 40 K by diffraction. The phase transition is clearly evidenced also in EXAFS spectra; its structural interpretation is under way, in cooperation with G. Artioli (Univ. Milano). The good quality of data allowed to refine the 2nd-shell analysis from 40 to 100 K. Actually, the 12 Ag atoms composing the 2nd shell can be grouped into two sets: 6 atoms are connected to the central Ag atom via an oxygen atom, and belong to the same network of tetrahedra (Type A); the other 6 Ag atoms belong to the other network (Type B). EXAFS shows that the Type A distance decreases, while Type B distance increases when temperature increases.

Measurements at the Cu K edge in Cu₂O have been done at GILDA in 2001, in the temperature range from 4 to 100 K. The measurements on Cu₂O were completed in 2002 at the beamline BM29, covering the range from 25 to 410 K (experiment HS-1720: BM29 was assigned in spite of an explicit request of BM08). The results obtained at BM29 are consistent with the results obtained at BM08 in the range of overlap (low temperatures). The results of the analysis basically confirm those of Ag₂O, although both positive and negative expansions are much weaker. In any case, negative and positive expansions are found for Type A and Type B 2nd-shell distances, respectively, also in Cu₂O.

Catalysis

The main groups working in catalysis on GILDA beamline came from the University of Palermo (I), University of Roma (I), University of Milano (I), University of Torino (I), University of Trieste,

University of Venezia, University of Pisa, from the ENI Technology SpA company in San Donato Milanese (I), from the ETH Zurich (CH) and from the Utrecht University (NL)

Most of the experiments used the first experimental hutch for EXAFS and XANES (occasionally REFLEXAFS) spectroscopies, but a relevant fraction of experiments were performed in the second hutch (diffraction hutch).

As can be easily seen, most of the GILDA's users came from the Italian catalytic community. In spite of its minority fraction, the international community is represented at its highest level.

Another important point to be mentioned concerns the fact that the GILDA beamline has been able to attract users coming from the industry, in particular, the ENI Technology SpA and the Polimeri Europa of the Istituto G. Donegani, Novara (I), the latter having mainly interacted with the Torino group.

It is important to mention that some groups didn't just play the role of users, but constructively collaborated with the beamline scientists, with their own money, knowledge and man-power, to the improvement of the experimental set-up available on the BM8 GILDA beamline to perform x-ray absorption and diffraction experiments on catalytic systems. In this regard we mention the cell developed by Lamberti et al.¹⁴⁴ for transmission XAFS measurements on catalysts in form of self supported pellets. This cell allows the activation of the samples up to 900 K in vacuum or in the desired atmosphere. Measurements are possible in the 77-900 K range, in vacuum, in presence of a constant desired equilibrium pressure or in a controlled flux of gases, which chemical composition can be measured by mass spectroscopy.

Another cell, suitable for in situ X-ray-absorption spectroscopy measurements of heterogeneous catalysts in both transmission and fluorescence modes has been designed, realized and tested by the Rome group¹⁴⁵. The cell, light and easy to handle, allows thermal treatments of the sample under investigation up to 823 K in a reducing or oxidizing atmosphere and measurements at both high and liquid-nitrogen temperature.

An Imaging-Plate camera for X-ray powder diffraction experiments was installed on the second hutch by GILDA group in strong collaboration with the Milano group¹⁴⁶. The IP camera can be used in fixed data-collection mode of the whole diffraction rings, or in translation mode for time-dependent experiments. The apparatus is ideal for collecting medium to relatively high-resolution diffraction data from diluted or weakly scattering samples and to investigate in situ phase changes induced by temperature and/or chemical reactions. The possibility to rapidly collect several good quality diffraction patterns coupled with tunable beam energy allow for multiwavelength experiments such as anomalous XRPD.

The group of Palermo have installed in the diffraction hutch a quadrupole mass spectrometer that can operate during the recording of the time-resolved X-ray diffraction pattern. The chemical and structural information can thus be combined¹⁴⁷

GILDA BM8 beamline attracted some of the Catalysis worldwide top groups and that some of them have undertaken a constructive collaboration, on both technical and scientific grounds, with the beamline staff. The last point is a fundamental to allow a continuous improvement of (i) the beamline itself and of (ii) the ability of the beamline staff to positively host new experiments characterized by increasing demanding requirements.

Hereafter studies performed by the different groups working on catalytic systems at GILDA are briefly described.

Results from the group of Palermo University (Martorana, Longo, Deganello et al.)

The Palermo group has been active both x-ray absorption and diffraction experiments on GILDA in strong collaboration with the beamline permanent and non permanent staff.

Nobel metals supported on pumice

Nobel metals supported on pumice have been widely investigated by this group: Rh¹⁴⁸, Ag-Pd bimetallic cluster^{149,150}. These studies combined EXAFS spectroscopy with anomalous small angle

scattering and powder XRD experiments performed on GILDA with other laboratory characterization techniques (XPS and TEM).

Pt/Ce-zirconia catalysts

Martorana et al. investigated, with time-resolved X-ray diffraction experiments⁹⁹, the structural modifications taking place in a Pt/Ce-zirconia catalyst while the CO oxidation reaction was in progress. The capillary tube in which the sample is stored acts effectively as a chemical microreactor that ensures homogeneity of the sample treatments and minimization of diffusion effects. During the flowing of the reactant CO/He mixture, the investigated catalyst undergoes a fast Ce(IV)-Ce(III) partial reduction that involves the release of one O atom for every two reduced Ce cations. Because Ce(III) has a larger ionic radius than Ce(IV), the structural modification produces an increase of the lattice constant of the ceria-zirconia mixed oxide, and this increase is monitored by the translating imaging-plate device implemented at GILDA. The CO₂ resulting from the oxidation of the fluxed CO is monitored by a quadrupole mass spectrometer during the recording of the time-resolved X-ray diffraction pattern. The chemical and structural information was combined to show that the CO₂ yield is nearly constant until the catalytic system can provide oxygen for the reaction, while the structural rearrangement of the catalyst is delayed with respect to the switching on of the CO/He flux. After this induction time, during which CO₂ is produced with no structural modification of the catalyst, a fast increase of the lattice constant takes place.

The structural evolution of two Pt/ceria-zirconia catalysts, characterized by different amounts of supported Pt, was monitored by in situ X-ray diffraction during the anaerobic oxidation of CO at different temperatures by Martorana et al.¹⁵¹. In a first phase, oxygen coming from the surface layers of the ceria-zirconia mixed oxide is consumed and no structural variation of the support is observed. After this induction time, bulk reduction of Pt/ceria-zirconia takes place as a step-like process, while the CO₂ production continues at a nearly constant rate. This behavior is totally different from that of the metal-free support in similar reaction conditions, that show a gradual bulk reduction. In repeated oxidation-reduction cycles, it was observed that the induction time in Pt/ceria-zirconia is a function of the thermal history, of the amount of supported Pt and of the structural evolution of the samples.

Results from the group of Roma University (Pettiti, Gazzoli, Inversi, Cimino et al.)

The group was very active in the study of perovskite-type oxides as potential catalysts^{152,153,154,155} and in the study of oxomolibdates supported on alumina¹⁵⁶.

In this last case they investigated the nature of the Co (or Ni) and Mo sulfided species obtained starting from γ -Al₂O₃-supported Anderson heteropolyoxomolybdates (CoMo₆ and NiMo₆) with EXAFS spectroscopy and TPR technique. Results obtained allow the authors to gain important knowledge in the catalytic activity for the thiophene hydrodesulfurization (HDS) reaction.

As for the perovskite oxide, in particular we quote the EXAFS and XRD experiments on La and Mn supported on ZrO₂. They reported¹⁰⁷ a detailed investigation of ZrO₂-supported La, Mn oxide catalysts with different La, Mn loading (0.7, 2, 4, 6, 12, and 16 wt% as LaMnO₃) prepared by impregnation. The catalysts were characterized by XRD, EXAFS and BET. The redox properties were tested by temperature-programmed reduction (TPR), and the catalytic tests were carried out for methane combustion at 650-1050 K and for CO oxidation at 350-800 K. XRD, revealed the presence of tetragonal zirconia with traces of the monoclinic phase. LaMnO₃ perovskite was also detected for loading higher than 6%. XAS and TPR experiments suggested that at high loading small crystallites of LaMnO₃, not uniformly spread on the zirconia surface, were formed; while at low loading, La, Mn oxide species interacting with the support, and hard to be structurally defined, prevailed. The catalysis study indicated that the presence of a perovskite-like structure is necessary for the development of highly active sites. Dilute catalysts were in fact poorly active even when considering the activity per gram of La, Mn perovskite-like composition. For methane combustion

and CO oxidation, similar trends of the activity as a function of the loading point to a similarity of the active sites for the two reactions on the examined catalytic system.

Very recently the group has reported an exhaustive study on δ - Al_2O_3 supported La, Mn, Co and Fe containing catalysts also prepared by impregnation¹⁵⁷. The catalysts were characterized by XR), UV-Vis DRS spectroscopy, EXAFS and BET. XRD revealed the presence of δ - Al_2O_3 in all cases and, at 30 wt.% of metal loading, of other single (α - Mn_2O_3 and α - Fe_2O_3) or mixed (LaAlO_3 , LaMnO_3 , CoAl_2O_4 and LaFeO_3) oxide phases. EXAFS suggested the formation of some oxide phases also at lower loading. In particular, all Mn and 10 wt.% La-Mn containing samples revealed the formation of α - Mn_2O_3 , while the 30 wt.% La-Mn bimetallic sample showed the formation of LaMnO_3 perovskite. All cobalt containing samples revealed the presence of CoAl_2O_4 spinel. Fe containing samples showed the formation of α - Fe_2O_3 , while La-Fe containing ones, that of LaFeO_3 perovskite. Catalytic tests of CO oxidation were performed in the temperature range 300-800 K. The sample containing 30 wt.% of La and Mn in the form of LaMnO_3 perovskite dispersed on δ - Al_2O_3 was found the most active among all the examined catalysts.

Results from the group of Milano University (Artioli et al.)

Highly productive is the Milano group which mainly performs XRPD experiments, but also collected and published EXAFS data.

EXAFS and XRD experiments on La, Mn supported on Ba- β - Al_2O_3 .

The crystal structure and, specifically the partitioning and the dominant oxidation state of Mn in the different crystallographic sites of Ba- β - Al_2O_3 has been clarified by means of EXAFS and XRPD structure refinements of multiple diffraction powder data sets collected with both synchrotron and Cu-K alpha radiation at different wave lengths in proximity and far from the Mn K adsorption edge¹⁵⁸. The results show that at low loading (up to $x=1$) Mn preferentially enters tetrahedral Al(2) sites of Ba- β - Al_2O_3 as divalent cation- The occupancy of Ba sites in the mirror planes acts as a charge compensation mechanism to balance substitution of Al^{3+} With Mn^{2+} . At high Mn loading the occupation of Ba sites reaches unity and Mn preferentially enters octahedral Al(1) sites as Mn^{3+} . Surface area measurements and catalytic activity tests in CH_4 combustion have also been performed. The results indicate that the incorporation of Mn in the octahedral Al(1) sites causes reduction of surface area and has no beneficial effect on catalytic activity.

In situ, time resolved, XRD experiments on nucleation of zeolitic frameworks.

The synthesis of zeolite LTA from a clear solution of nominal composition $8.6\text{Na}_2\text{O}_{0.18}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2\text{-150H}_2\text{O}$ was in situ investigated by Artioli et al.¹⁵⁹ using a combination of dynamic light scattering and XRPD techniques. Important information on the early stages of the nucleation process have been obtained. The experiments were performed at temperatures ranging between 60 and 100 °C. The dynamic light scattering data clearly show at all temperatures the rapid development of an amorphous phase which consistently precedes the appearance of the LTA crystals. The observation of the amorphous precursor, the delayed formation of the crystalline zeolite, and the analysis of the kinetic parameters of the process indicate that the nucleation process of zeolite LTA from clear solution is heterogeneous and occurs at the interface between the solution and the amorphous precursor.

Investigations on the nucleation and growth processes of Linde type A zeolite (LTA) from clear solution were performed both in situ using synchrotron XRPD on small volume samples contained in capillaries and ex situ using laboratory XRPD on samples synthesized from large volume vessels¹⁶⁰. Isothermal experiments were performed in the temperature range 60-90 °C. The well known LTA system was selected in order to define the nucleation and growth mechanisms and kinetic parameters, and to critically compare the results of the kinetic analysis obtained by two rather different methods of investigation, The kinetic modeling of the in situ and ex situ isothermal diffraction data indicate that (i) the nucleation mechanisms are the same whether occurring in small-

volume or large-volume syntheses; and (ii) despite earlier claims of homogeneous nucleation mechanisms, the nucleation process is heterogeneous and invariably involves the formation of an amorphous precursor. All syntheses products associated with zeolite LTA (that is faujasite and hydroxylsodalite type zeolites) have been characterized by XRPD and scanning electron microscopy analyses.

In situ, time resolved, XRD experiments on template burning in zeolitic frameworks.

This study is a collaboration among University of Milano (G. Artioli), University of Modena (A. Gualtieri); University of Alesandria (M. Milanesio), ESRF (L. Palin) and University of Torino (C. Lamberti). The high X-ray flux available at the ESRF, combined with the use of a suitably designed area detector setup available on the GILDA BM8 beamline allowed Milanesio et al.^{161,162} to follow in real time by XRPD the structural changes occurring during the template burning processes inside TS-1 and Fe-MFI zeolites (see Figure 17a). The Rietveld full structure analysis yields the template occupancy factor vs. T (full line, left axis) in good agreement with the thermogravimetric data (Figure 17b, solid squares, right axis). The model for the refinement of the template molecule derives from the single crystal XRD study performed on ID11 beamline [Palin, et al. J. Phys. Chem. B, 107 (2003) 4034].

Figure 17

- (a): Evolution of the XRPD patterns in the 2.5-12.5° 2θ-interval (corresponding to 14.2-2.8 Å d-spacing) as a function of the temperature during the *in situ* template burning of TS-1, $\lambda = 0.82667(6)$ Å. Main reflections have been indicated.
- (b) Direct comparison between the refined TPA⁺ occupancy factor (scattered red squares, right axis) and the per cent loss of weight (continuous blue line, left axis) during the template burning process inside TS-1. Adapted from Milanesio, et al. JACS 125 (2003) 14549; ESRF Highlights 125 (2003) 113.

Figure 18

Evolution of the cell volume (a) and the lattice parameters for both TS-1 (b) and Fe-MFI (c) during the *in situ* template burning in the 300-1000 K range plotted as $V(T)/V_0$, $a(T)/a_0$, $b(T)/b_0$, and $c(T)/c_0$ (being the reference values obtained at 350 and 340 K for TS-1 and Fe-MFI, respectively). Reproduced from Milanesio, et al. JACS 125 (2003) 14549.

By monitoring the evolution of the a , b and c cell axes vs. temperature (Figure 18) it has been observed that the volume changes anisotropically during the whole process, for both TS-1 and Fe-MFI, following the inequalities $b(T)/b_0 < c(T)/c_0 \ll a(T)/a_0$, being a_0 , b_0 and c_0 the starting lattice parameters. These results imply that the zeolite crystals are subject to remarkable stress forces during the process, and that the strong anisotropic contraction contributes to crack formation in the zeolite crystals. These data allow us to have, for the first time, a complete view of the structural rearrangements induced by the template burning process on the zeolitic framework. Isothermal runs have also been performed, and the results of the kinetic analysis indicated that the template burning is a diffusion limited reaction with monodimensional advancement. The rate limiting step of the reaction is the diffusion of the volatile products of the template burning out of the crystal. Chemical and steric considerations indicate that the straight channels along the b axis are the more favorable direction for the molecule diffusion and removal. Corresponding Arrhenius plots result in an apparent activation energy values of $151 \pm 11 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$ and of $159 \pm 7 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$ for TS-1 and Fe-MFI, respectively.

Results from the group of Trieste University (Vlaic Fornasiero, Fonda, Graziani et al.)

The Trieste group studies the problem of multielectron excitation in the data analysis of Ce L₃ edge¹⁶³ an important aspect of data analysis in general and of catalytic systems in particular.

In collaboration with the University of Milano and with the CNR of Milano (Psaro, Sordelli et al.) they reported¹⁶⁴ also on the influence of the cationic promoters (M = Li, Na, K, Rb, Cs) of silica-supported rhodium catalysts in the hydroformylation of propene at 413 K and atmospheric pressure. The catalysts were prepared by aqueous co-impregnation of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and alkali-metal chloride. The rhodium to promoter molar ratio was 1. A pre-treatment cycle under $\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2$ at 673 K was carried out on the catalyst before the admission of the hydroformylation mixture. By in situ Rh K-edge EXAFS characterization of the activated catalyst, two different Rh and alkali-metal oxide phases, highly dispersed and in intimate contact with each other, were detected on the support surface. Under catalytic conditions, small Rh metal particles are formed, with a mean diameter of 3.2 nm, as detected by HRTEM. The activity in aldehyde formation depends on the alkali-metal promoter in the following order: $\text{Li} > \text{Na} > \text{K} > \text{Rb}$ much greater than Cs.

Results from the group of ETH Zurich (Prins et al.)

EXAFS studies on Rh and Pt and bimetallic Ph-Pt clusters on zeolite NaY.

The size and shape of monometallic Rh and Pt and bimetallic Ph-Pt clusters on zeolite NaY were determined with EXAFS spectroscopy by Cimino and Prins^{165,166}. Data collected at GILDA BM8 and at Darsbury are reported in this study. Authors found that in the monometallic as well as in the bimetallic samples, the first coordination numbers were independent of the metal loading (1.5-4.8 wt % for Pt and 0.8-2.5 wt % for Ph in monometallic samples, and 0.8-2.4 wt % for Pt and 0.4-1.2 wt % for Ph in the bimetallic samples). All first coordination numbers were around 7, demonstrating that all monometallic and bimetallic particles have similar dimensions. The second- and third-shell coordination numbers of the monometallic clusters are in accordance with a spherical shape of the metal clusters which just fit into the supercages of the Y zeolite structure. Both Rh and Pt have the tendency to bind preferentially to their own kind. The observed coordination numbers, as well as the EXAFS spectra obtained after CO absorption, showed that no substantial surface enrichment is present in the bimetallic RhPt/NaY samples.

EXAFS investigation of SiO₂ supported NiMo catalyst

The structure of nickel and molybdenum in silica-supported NiMo catalyst precursors, modified by the addition of various chelating ligands, was studied by the Prins group using EXAFS, Raman, and UV-VIS spectroscopy^{167,168}. Data collected at GILDA BM8 and BM01 are reported in this study. Thiophene hydrodesulfurization tests showed that a wide variety of ligands have a beneficial

effect on the performance of the sulfided catalysts. The activity of catalysts prepared with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and ethylenediamine (EN) was measured as a function of the ligand to Ni ratio in the catalyst precursors as well. Authors showed that EN gradually causes an improvement of the catalytic activity when the EN/Ni molar ratio increases from 0 to 4, while the best result for NTA is obtained when the NTA/Ni ratio is 1.5. UV-VIS spectra of NiMoEN impregnation solutions and dried catalysts showed that some EN is removed from the first coordination sphere of Ni during the drying procedure. Ni K-edge extended EXAFS proved the presence of a Ni-Si shell and, thus, of Ni-SiO₂ interactions in the catalyst precursors prepared without ligands. These interactions disappeared gradually with increasing amounts of the ligand. Raman spectroscopy and Mo K-edge EXAFS showed that Mo is present on the support as a mixture of MoO₄²⁻ and polymolybdate clusters. Raman spectroscopy also suggested that these polymolybdate clusters interact with the support. Mo K-edge EXAFS spectra showed that EN has very little effect on Mo, whereas at NTA concentrations higher than 1 the [MoO₃(NTA)]³⁻ complex is formed. The increase in activity obtained with EN and NTA is attributed to the elimination of Ni-SiO₂ interactions and to the presence of the ligands in the Ni coordination sphere, whereas the decrease in activity observed in catalysts with NTA/Ni ratios above 2 is explained by the formation of [MoO₃(NTA)]³⁻.

Results from the group of Venezia University (Riello, Canton et al.)

Thermal evolution of Carbon supported Pd clusters

The Venezia group, in collaboration with the GILDA scientists, reported a time-resolved X-ray diffraction study, performed in situ, on a Pd/C catalyst during two successive thermal treatments from 300 to 873 K¹⁶⁹. Analysis of the diffraction patterns, as a function of thermal treatment, reveals anomalous features in the evolution of Pd particles. An intermediate Pd_{1-x}C_x phase ($x \sim 0.1$) is observed and dissolved into pure Pd at ~ 700 K. Moreover, the size of metal particles, remaining almost constant (~ 10 nm) during the annealing, abruptly increases to 30 nm in close connection with the dissolution of the Pd_{1-x}C_x phase. These effects clearly point out an interaction between the metal and the support and suggest that the formation of the Pd_{1-x}C_x phase would prevent the metal-particle sintering, thus maintaining the catalyst dispersion at a high level. There is no evidence of the formation of a Pd_{1-x}C_x phase during the second temperature treatment since only metallic Pd was detected. As for the growth in particle size, a small increase to 32 nm was observed. The same group studied also the nanostructure of Pd/SiO₂ supported catalysts¹⁷⁰

Results from the Eni Technology SpA group (Millini et al.)

Millini et al performed a very detailed study on experiments (08-02-155 and 08-02-175) describing an high quality XRPD study on Ti-silicalite (TS-1) and B-silicalite catalysts. Data have been acquired using both the conventional step-scanning two circle diffractometer (Debye-Sherrer geometry) and image plate detection systems. Rietveld refinements, performed on both data sets, were of high quality. The results are described in a very accurate and long (10 pages) report; unfortunately a final publication in an international journal, summarizing all this nice work is still missing.

Results from the group of Torino University (Lamberti, Bordiga, Zecchina, Prestipino, Groppo, Berlier et al.)

EXAFS and high resolution XANES results on Cu-exchanged zeolites.

Copper-exchanged molecular sieves have been widely investigated after the discovery that Cu-ZSM-5 are active in the direct decomposition of nitric oxide to nitrogen and oxygen. The group has deeply investigated Cu-exchanged zeolites with EXAFS and XANES data collected in situ at the

GILDA BM8 beamline¹⁷¹⁻¹⁸⁴. Synchrotron radiation data have been supported by parallel laboratory techniques such as IR, UV-Vis, photoluminescence, EPR, and microcalorimetry.

Figure 19

Part (a) XANES spectra of Cu-MOR thermally treated at increasing temperatures: 300 K (full line), 373 K (dashed line), 473 K (dotted line), 573 K (dotted-dashed line), and 673 K (bold full line). For comparison the spectrum of a Cu^+ -ZSM-5 model compound (line-square curve) is also included. The inset reports the magnification of the $1s \rightarrow 3d$ electronic transition of Cu^{2+} species. Part (b) reports the corresponding derivative spectra (same drawing as in part a). For the sake of clarity spectra have been vertically shifted. For every curve a horizontal dotted line represents the corresponding zero level. Reproduced from Llabrés i Xamena et al. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (2003) 7036.

The Torino's group has been able to investigate the interaction of different probe molecules such as N_2 , CO , NH_3 on different Cu-Zeolites (ZSM5, Y, Mordenite, β and ferrierite) in the 77-300 K temperature range. Of great relevance have been the high resolution XANES spectra that allowed to follow the variation of the geometrical and electronic features of Cu species upon molecules adsorption. The $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \leftrightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ redox cycle undergone by the catalyst during activation (Figure 19) and interaction with NO (Figure 20). On a technical ground, the dipole forbidden $1s \rightarrow 3d$ electronic transition of Cu^{2+} species has been observed in the spectra with a spectroscopic definition never measured before. Note that we are dealing with a forbidden transition which intensity is less than 0.03 in normalized μ_x units.

Figure 20

Part (a) XANES spectra of Cu-MOR thermally treated at 673 K (dotted line); after interaction with NO at 77 K (\blacktriangle , $P_{\text{NO}} = 8$ Torr); the system was then allowed to reach in NO atmosphere at room temperature and subsequently outgassed (dashed line); for comparison also the spectrum of the starting Cu-MOR sample outgassed at room temperature is included (full line). Part (b) reports the corresponding derivative spectra (same drawing as in part a). For the sake of clarity, the spectra have been vertically shifted. For every curve a horizontal dotted line represents the corresponding zero level. The inset in part a) corresponds to the EPR spectrum of the Cu-MOR sample thermally treated at 673 K in interaction with NO ($P_{\text{NO}} = 0.1$ Torr) at 77 K. Reproduced from Llabrés i Xamena et al. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (2003) 7036.

Lamberti et al. have been able to follow in situ the $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ oxidation occurring on the living catalyst when the NO decomposition reaction starts ($2\text{NO} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2$) on both Cu-ZSM-5 and Cu-Mordenite systems. The NO molecules have been dosed on the activated zeolite at liquid nitrogen temperature. Under such conditions the decomposition reaction does not take place and a stable $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{NO})_2$ adduct has been observed (scattered triangles in Figure 20). The formation of $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{NO})_2$ adduct breaks the local symmetry of Cu^{I} ions in vacuo and resulted in the removal of the degeneration of copper $4p$ orbitals evidenced by the appearance of three pre-edge features ascribed to $1s \rightarrow 4p_x$, $1s \rightarrow 4p_y$ and $1s \rightarrow 4p_z$ electronic transitions. By allowing the cell temperature to reach room temperature the NO decomposition reaction is progressively switched on and as monitored by the appearance of XANES features typical of Cu^{II} cations hosted in zeolitic channels (dashed line in Figure 4). The same experiment, followed in situ by IR spectroscopy revealed the decrease of the IR bands due to the N-O stretching in $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{NO})_2$ adducts, the appearance of complexes $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{NO})$ adduct and appearance of the oxidation products.

EXAFS and high resolution XANES results on TS-1 Catalyst

Titanium sicalite-1 (TS-1) is a synthetic zeolite in which a small number of Ti atoms substitute tetrahedral Si atoms in a purely siliceous framework with the MFI structure. It is an active and highly selective catalyst in a number of low-temperature oxidation reactions, with aqueous H_2O_2 as the oxidant agent. Among all we shall mention: the conversions of ammonia to hydroxylamine, of

secondary alcohols to ketones, of secondary amines to dialkylhydroxylamines, or reactions such as phenol hydroxylation, olefin epoxidation, or cyclohexanone ammoximation.

High resolution XANES spectra of TS-1 have been first reported by the Torino's group in a paper appeared on JACS in 2001¹⁸⁵. More recently Prestipino et al.¹⁸⁶ have reported an experimental breakthrough in the study of TS-1 in interaction with H₂O₂ as they were able to dose, in situ on the activated catalyst from the gas phase (using KH₂PO₄·H₂O₂ as hydrogen peroxide source) an almost anhydrous H₂O₂ vapor to the TS-1 catalyst. The XANES spectrum of TS-1 contacted with anhydrous H₂O₂ from the gas phase gave results very similar to that obtained after prolonged evacuation, at 77 K, of the TS-1 sample previously contacted with H₂O₂/H₂O from the liquid phase [Bordiga et al., J. Phys. Chem. B. 106 (2002) 9892]. Finally, when water is added to the uncolored catalyst, previously contacted with anhydrous H₂O₂, it turns yellow and its XANES spectrum possesses the fingerprint features of the side on Ti-peroxo species. Scheme 1 shows that in the equilibrium between the uncolored end-on η^1 Ti-hydroperoxo complex and the yellow colored side-on η^2 Ti-peroxo complex is tuned by the amount of water present in the channels. The EXAFS part of the x-ray absorption spectrum confirms the picture emerged from UV-Vis DRS and XANES: anhydrous H₂O₂ modifies significantly the first coordination around Ti, leaving the second one almost unaffected (compare dotted and dashed lines). Conversely, when H₂O is added a complete modification of both first and second shell signals is observed, which has been interpreted in terms of the rupture of a Ti-O-Si bridge. The new data suggest that this effect is not present in anhydrous conditions.

Scheme 1 – Representation of equilibria between TiO₄ framework species and η^1 complexes inside TS-1 channels upon dosage of anhydrous H₂O₂ (left) and between η^1 and η^2 complexes upon hydration (right).

On a technical ground, the results obtained on TS-1 catalyst are very important because they prove that, with the appropriate use of mirrors, high quality XANES and EXAFS results can be obtained on diluted samples as low as Ti K-edge (5 keV) on the GILDA beamline. This is far to be trivial for a beamline that works on a bending magnet which critical energy is close to 20 keV and that is able to work up to 50 keV.

EXAFS and high resolution XANES results on Fe-zeolite catalysts

Fe-zeolites have proved their utility and selectivity in several partial oxidation reactions using N₂O as oxidant such as the oxidation of methane to methanol and the oxidation of benzene to phenol. They are also employed in the de-NO_x catalysis.

From 2002, some important new results have been obtained by the Torino's group on this catalytic system using EXAFS and high resolution XANES data collected at the GILDA BM8 beamline^{187,188,189,190,191}. The investigated Fe-silicalite samples had a sufficient iron dilution (Si/Fe = 90) to be considered "true" catalysts in partial oxidation reactions (e.g. benzene to phenol). It has been shown that Fe³⁺ species are incorporated, during zeolite synthesis in framework Si sites, where they exhibit a tetrahedral symmetry being coordinated to four oxygen atoms of the lattice. Template burning in air and sample activation in vacuo causes a progressive migration of ordered iron from

framework sites into disordered extraframework positions. This phenomenon is associated to a reduction from Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} . The fraction of iron species involved in this phenomenon depends upon the activation temperature, and can reach the value of one when severe treatments are adopted. The structural disorder of extraframework Fe species is monitored by the striking decrease of the EXAFS signal, while the changes of the oxidation state has been indicated in the XANES part of the X-ray absorption spectra. So obtained extraframework Fe^{2+} species are characterized by very high coordinative unsaturation, being able to form $\text{Fe}^{2+}(\text{NO})_3$ complexes upon interaction with NO at RT (as evidenced by IR spectra). Interaction with N_2O at 523 K causes the overall re-oxidation of iron species resulting in a catalyst containing extraframework species characterized by a less pronounced coordinative unsaturation. IR spectroscopy shows the dissociation of N_2O , while EXAFS spectroscopy shows the increase of the coordination sphere of iron. This fact has been interpreted in terms of an additional oxygen atom (coming from the decomposition of N_2O) coordinated to Fe^{3+} species. The described $\text{Fe}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$ redox cycle has been qualitatively followed by EPR spectroscopy also.

EXAFS and high resolution XANES results on Cr-SiO₂: the Phillips catalyst

The Cr/SiO₂ Phillips catalysts, patented in 1958 by Hogan and Banks are nowadays responsible for the commercial production of more than one third of all the polyethylene sold world-wide. Notwithstanding its industrial importance and the numerous efforts, the structure of active sites on the Phillips-type systems and the polymerization mechanism remain controversial. This is the reason why the Torino's group has very recently performed experiments at the GILDA beamline on this system^{192,193}.

In this first *in situ* EXAFS and XANES study on the Phillips ethylene-polymerization Cr/SiO₂ catalyst two polymerization routes are investigated and compared. The first mimics that adopted in industrial plants, where ethylene is dosed directly on the oxidized catalyst, while in the second the oxidized catalyst is first reduced by CO at 623 K. On this reduced catalyst the C₂H₄ polymerization has been investigated at room temperature as well as at 373 K (Figure 21). Although already unpublished, these results are so important that they have already been included in an important review article that will appear soon on Chemical Review.

In collaboration with the Eindhoven University (NL) (Profs. P. C. Thüne, and J. W. Niemantsverdriet) and with the beamline scientists (F. D'Acapito) preliminary RefLEXAFS experiments have been performed on a model catalyst prepared by impregnation of Cr on a flat Si(100) substrate covered by a thin layer of amorphous silica. Experiments have been performed *ex situ* on the grafted catalyst (*i.e.* after impregnation and thermal activation) and at the end of the polymerization stage. High quality XANES data have been collected on a sample with a surface Cr content of 4 Cr atoms per 100 Å². 15 shifts have recently been allocated by the ESRF Chemistry review Committee to continue this promising and challenging REFLEXAFS experiment.

Figure 21

Part (a): high resolution XANES spectra of the Cr/SiO₂ Phillips catalyst after oxidation at 773 K (black dotted line) and subsequent reduction in CO at 623 K (black line). For comparison also the spectra of CrO₃ (dotted gray line) and of α-Cr₂O₃ (gray line) model compounds are reported. The inset reports a magnification of the pre-edge features; here also the spectrum of the [Cr(OCOCH₃)₂ H₂O]₂ model compound is reported (dashed line). Part (b): High resolution XANES spectra of the catalyst after in situ polymerization. The dashed line and the dash-dotted line spectra refer to the CO reduced sample, subsequently contacted with C₂H₄ at RT and at 373 K, respectively. The scattered square line refers to the Cr/SiO₂ catalyst directly reduced in C₂H₄ at 523 K for 1 h (ethylene-reduced catalyst). As an example of unengaged Cr(II) species, the spectrum collected on the CO reduced catalyst (prior contact with ethylene) is also reported (full line). The inset reports a magnification of the pre-edge features. Part (c): Modulus of the k²-weighted, phase uncorrected, Fourier transform (2-11 Å⁻¹ range) of the EXAFS signal collected on the Cr/SiO₂ catalyst in different conditions: oxidized (dotted line); reduced in CO at 623 K (full line); after subsequent polymerization at RT (dashed line); Cr/SiO₂ catalyst directly reduced in C₂H₄ at 523 K for 1 h (ethylene-reduced catalyst, scattered square line). The inset reports, with the same symbols, the corresponding imaginary parts. Adapted from Groppo et al. *J. Catal.*, submitted; Groppo et al. *Chem. Rev.* in press.

Results from the group of Pisa University (Pertici, Vitulli et al.)

The Pisa group studied Rhodium nanoparticles¹⁹⁴ supported on g-Al₂O₃, derived from arene-solvated Rh atoms stabilized by trioctylamine (TOA). They studied also a sample prepared in a similar way but in the absence of TOA. These systems are valuable catalysts in hydrogenation and silylformylation reactions and are largely more active than the analogous commercial catalysts. HRTEM measurements, IR studies on adsorbed CO species and extended X-ray absorption fine structure analyses evidenced the role of TOA in controlling the particle growth in the preparative process and in stabilizing the resulting Rh particles against erosion by CO and oxidation

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